

Review article

State-of-the-art circular economy practices for end-of-life wind turbine blades for use in the construction industry

Ashal Tyurkay, Gunvor M. Kirkelund, Ana Teresa Macas Lima*

Department of Environment and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, 2800 Lyngby, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Prof. Konstantinos Tsagarakis

Keywords:

Wind turbine blades
Decommissioning
Recycling
End-of-life
Circular economy
Construction

ABSTRACT

The transition towards carbon neutrality by 2050 in the European Union and the subsequent increase of windpower is anticipated to lead to a significant increase in fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) waste generated by end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades (WTBs). Most of this waste is being landfilled due to legislative and material challenges, and a lack of sustainable materials management strategies. In this study, we reviewed the status quo of EoL WTB for their constituent materials, expected quantities per country, waste treatment technologies, supply chain, and circular options for EoL. We proposed a framework for incorporating circular economy (CE) principles in the EoL management for WTBs and assessed the readiness of the wind industry for sustainable decommissioning and circularity. Using the circularity ladder concept, we categorized waste prevention strategies, treatment technologies, and secondary uses of EoL WTB waste. We questioned the suitability of the construction industry for cross-sectoral CE and looked into emerging material innovations.

Circular economy and wind energy can be developed in synergy as part of sustainable transitions to find innovative uses for EoL WTB materials in construction and to improve EoL management of WTBs. The results, however, highlight a lack of knowledge and experience in decommissioning practices. Effective decommissioning handling requires an integrative approach where the technological development in WTB waste treatment and their economic aspects are based on the quantities and location of waste streams and material flows. Environmental and legislative factors largely influence these aspects. Due to this intricacy of the decommissioning phase, we should emphasize the role of supply chain responsibility and collaboration along the WTB manufacturing-collection-demolition continuum, reflecting the whole lifecycle of WTBs into the EoL.

1. Introduction

The EU is facing the transition towards carbon neutrality by 2050 as per the Paris Agreement (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2015) and resolving energy security issues that emerged after Ukraine's occupation in 2022. Governments urgently need to shift to a cleaner and more secure energy system based on renewable energy. One of these plans is to increase wind power, resulting in a considerable increase in new wind farms and repowering projects, i.e., replacing old wind turbines with more efficient and bigger turbines.

In 1982, the first worldwide three-bladed 22 kW-wind turbine model

was installed (IRENA, 2019), and in 1991, the first offshore wind farm started its operations in Vindeby, Denmark (IRENA, 2019). Considering an operational life span of 20 years and that average onshore wind turbine ratings were improved to exceed 1 MW just recently in 2001 (IRENA, 2019), we can assume that only a few wind farms have come to the end of their operating lifetime. On the other hand, as of 2020, the total installed capacity of wind power in Europe was 631.1 GW (IEA Wind, 2020a, 2020b), and about 4 GW of capacity was decommissioned the same year (WindEurope, 2020a, 2020b). The total repowering volume is expected to grow from 1 to 2 GW in 2017 to 5.5–8.5 GW by 2027 in Europe's most mature wind markets, e.g., the UK, Germany, Denmark, Spain, etc. (WindEurope, 2017). Repowering occurs either

Abbreviations: EoL, End-of-life; WTB, Wind turbine blade; FRP, Fiber-reinforced plastics; MW, Mega-watt; GW, Giga-watt; CE, Circular Economy; GFRP, Glass-FRP; CFRP, Carbon-FRP; HVF, High voltage pulse fragmentation; HVFCarbon fiber, CF; GF, Glass fiber; vGF, Virgin glass fiber; vCF, Virgin carbon fiber; EPR, Extended Producer Responsibility; OEMs, Original Equipment Manufacturers; DP, Decommissioning Plan; SMC/BMC, Compound/Sheet molding compound; LCA, Life cycle assessment.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: atmli@dtu.dk (A.T.M. Lima).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.03.018>

Received 1 October 2023; Received in revised form 14 March 2024; Accepted 16 March 2024

Available online 22 March 2024

2352-5509/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Institution of Chemical Engineers. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

because of the end of the technical lifetime of the wind turbines or, as in most cases, a response to the regulatory framework demand for increased wind power where old turbines up to 1 MW are replaced with 3–4 MW turbines or even upcoming models (>5 MW for onshore, 15–20 MW for offshore) (WindEurope, 2017; IRENA, 2019). Due to the significant disparity between installation and decommissioning numbers, there is room for improvement in the knowledge and experience of wind farm operators concerning the decommissioning process (Topham and McMillan, 2017).

Several components of wind turbines such as the foundation, tower, nacelle, and generator can be recycled. There is a critical need for well-established and effective methods for dealing with end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades (WTB). The increasing trend in the average rated capacity (MW) indicates that turbine sizes and blade lengths also increase with time. Calculations estimate 200,000 and 500,000 tons/year of WTB waste globally by 2033 (Beauson et al., 2016) and 2050 (Liu and Barlow, 2017), respectively – with a share of 325,000 tons/year in Europe in 2050 (Lichtenegger et al., 2020). This will generate around 43.4 Mtons WTB waste worldwide by 2050 (Liu and Barlow, 2017). The European EoL WTB waste generated only in the year 2050 corresponds to the total weight of 1710 typical average commercial aircraft, and the global sum of EoL WTB by 2050 equals 230,000 aircraft (Pierce and Falzon, 2017; Welsch, 2022).

Methods of lifecycle assessment (LCA) for lifetime extension and reuse of EoL WTB in its original function after repair and maintenance are still immature for effective implementation (IEA Wind, 2020b). Repurposing the whole or sections of WTB structure in infrastructure, buildings, or other architectural products is difficult to implement on an industrial scale (Nagle et al., 2022). Some studies investigate repurposing the mechanically processed fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) material as a filler or a reinforcement in concrete or asphalt without changing its composite structure (Yazdanbakhsh and Bank, 2014). Others explore and develop thermal or chemical recycling technologies to reclaim either fibers or polymers that are not yet economically viable and scalable (GWEC, 2022). However, most of the WTB waste is currently being landfilled, and it will continue to be landfilled. The main reasons for landfilling are: (i) insufficient legislation for sustainable waste management of wind energy systems (Beauson, 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; IEA Wind, 2020a); and (ii) challenges inherent to WTB material composition, which is mainly made of FRP.

It is crucial to develop innovative uses for EoL WTB materials and find alternatives to improve the EoL management process of wind turbines. Circular Economy (CE) integration into the wind industry at the EoL management of FRP composites has revealed important gaps in decommissioning (Jensen et al., 2020; Velenturf, 2021). From an industrial perspective, the wind industry is looking to couple its efforts with other sectors to (re)use the decommissioned materials from wind farms to maximize the environmental benefits through life cycle approaches (WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020). In a Circular Supply Chain, resource input, waste, and emission leakage are minimized, and a set of conceptual business models improves operative effectiveness and efficiency to preserve the inherent value of products by increased cycling of product and material chains as long as feasible in alignment with the definitions of European Commission (2014). Reframing EoL management of FRP WTB waste in a CE is possible in practice by implementing strategies described with R-ladders, i.e., refuse, reduce, reuse, recycle, or a variation thereof, the most famous one being R10 by Potting et al. (2017).

An extensive number of studies are analyzed to exemplify the corresponding circular strategy in Section 3.5 Circular Economy of wind turbine blades for construction, Table 5. The majority of these studies are in the construction industry. The construction industry is indeed a perfect candidate for cross-sectoral circularity, as buildings are responsible for 39 % of global carbon emissions, and embodied carbon emissions associated with construction materials and processes will account for more than half of the entire carbon footprint of new construction

between now and 2050 (WorldGBC, 2019). The symbiosis between the two industries – construction and wind energy – will reveal the potential of the WTB waste created in the wind industry and may contribute to the development of circular construction materials, thus lowering the construction industry's carbon footprint.

We urgently need solutions to the increasing waste stream from the wind industry. In this context, we performed a literature review and created a framework: (i) EoL WTB for their constituent materials, (ii) expected quantities per country, (iii) waste treatment technologies, (iv) supply chain and (v) circular options for EoL. Using this framework, we identified the following gaps: lack of material WTBs composition data; uncertain decommissioning numbers and volumes of future WTB waste; uncertain technologies and their capacity to treat WTB FRP waste; complex challenges in decommissioning of WTBs; and lack of responsibility in the decommissioning of WTB and their stakeholders. Continued research, collaboration, and development of best practices are essential to address the challenges and fully realize the potential of circularity in wind and construction industries.

2. Methodology

We performed a literature review (LR) based on the methodology proposed by Okoli and Schabram (2010) (Fig. 1).

2.1. Planning and data collection

After defining the purpose of this research and formulating the research questions with the protocol as in Step 1 and 2 in Fig. 1, we identified the keywords to retrieve literature. Primarily, we used DTU FindIt platform (DTU Library, n.d.), which offers up-to-date open access or licensed content by DTU and beyond from providers including but not limited to Elsevier, Scopus, Taylor & Francis, and Web of Science (WoS). Iteratively in 2023, we searched using the keywords “End-of-life wind turbine blades”, “Wind turbine blade waste”, and “Wind decommissioning”, which we interpreted as “kw: End-of-life AND wind AND turbine AND blades”, “kw: Wind AND turbine AND blade AND waste”, and “kw: Wind AND kw: Decommissioning”, respectively. Our search yielded 203 hits, with 32, 122, and 49 results for each keyword. We expanded the data collection by including market overview reports and statistics from WindEurope and The Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) – two of the prominent international trade associations in the wind industry, as well as reports from research projects and consortia, such as International Energy Agency (IEA), DecomBlades, and The Energy Transition Alliance Blade Recycling Project, among others. The inclusion of the additional reports provided insights into the wind industry from a sectorial lens and enriched the data for WTB waste numbers.

2.2. Data analysis and synthesis

We assessed the quality of the studies to determine which ones serve the aim of this research. For the initial screening, we looked for answers to the research questions defined in Step 2. We categorized each study regarding waste treatment options, stages, and processes listed and whether it was relevant to the CE and/or the construction industry. Additionally, we categorized the studies as whether they investigated these topics' technical, economic, environmental, or legislative aspects. To filter the articles, we read each one in three stages. First, we reviewed the title and abstract. Secondly, we read the introduction and conclusion; thirdly, we read the entire article. Through this iterative process and excluding the duplicates, we identified 101 studies that met our selection criteria.

Step 4 Synthesis: Synthesis of the studies focused on analyzing the technical, economic, environmental, legislative, and design aspects of sustainability related to the handling of WTB waste, which was grouped into five subject categories (Fig. 2). These categories are described in Fig. 4 with the number of studies for each. Furthermore, each study's

Fig. 1. Overall approach for the literature review.

Fig. 2. Thematic categorization of the analyzed studies.

Circularity “R” categories were defined based on the waste treatment method and how the WTBs are used as a second-generation product in the construction industry. The quantitative synthesis of the studies helped identify areas where more research is needed among the five subjects and circularity categories in terms of sustainability aspects defined in this review. The qualitative synthesis of the studies, on the other hand, mapped out the key findings and results of the LR, providing critical input for the writing of this review (Step 5). The findings of the LR were summarized in a conceptual framework for circular EoL strategies for WTBs.

3. Literature review

101 selected studies were categorized into five subjects (Fig. 2) as presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

CE is possible when another industry could benefit from the use of EoL FRP material that is discarded as waste in the wind industry to manufacture a new product. 15 out of 41 CE category-studies on EoL WTB indicate that the construction sector is closer to cross-sectoral circularity (Fig. 5). Four of these studies relate to manufacturing businesses useful for the construction industry, such as second-generation composite fabrication, 3D printing, and bulk molding compound/sheet molding compound (SMC/BMC). The rest of the studies are not specific to any industry, making the construction industry highly feasible to increase its efforts in EoL WTB circularity.

3.1. End-of-life fiber-reinforced plastic blade materials

A typical WTB comprises balsa wood, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) foam

Fig. 3. Categorization of the studies according to main subjects and the quantitative distribution of sustainability aspects incorporated as a research element.

Fig. 4. Description of subject categories and the sustainable aspects and the number of studies.

Fig. 5. Sectoral categorization of CE studies in the literature.

or polyethylene terephthalate (PET) foam core, and fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)— mostly glass or carbon fibers that reinforce a thermoset polymer matrix, such as epoxy or polyester. It incorporates several layers of in-mold or post-mold coatings (Cortés et al., 2017). The primary material used in WTB is FRP, which comprises a combination of fibers, resin, and adhesives that account for approximately 92 % of the total blade weight (Liu and Barlow, 2016). Studies show that the

composition and heterogeneity of the blade material pose challenges for EoL WTB waste downstream treatment. One of the main issues is using structural adhesive in connections and joints, which complicates the disassembly process. The polymer matrix, which accounts for 30–40 % of the FRP content (WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020), is a thermoset material that exhibits combustibility and lacks remoldability. Reinforcements, making up 60–70 % of the combination of FRP, are

therefore difficult to separate.

In our data/literature search, we encountered a scarcity of studies on recyclability and reusability of FRP blade materials. 5 out of 15 studies come from industry reports, position papers, or technical reports prepared for or in collaboration with the industry (Skelton, 2017; Ierides and Reiland, 2019; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020; Bennet et al., 2021; Bennet et al., 2022). The rest comes from academic research to provide a qualitative or quantitative basis for the discussion of the recyclability of the material (Beauson and Brøndsted, 2016; Jensen and Skelton, 2018; Juntikka et al., 2018; Topham et al., 2019a; Liu et al., 2019; Mattsson et al., 2020; Sommer et al., 2020; Dorigato, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2023).

A serious challenge regarding the maintenance and EoL interventions for FRP stems from the limited material knowledge and experience surrounding the EoL management of WTB, which can be attributed partly to their relatively recent emergence and novelty within the field. FRP materials originated in the 1940s, primarily in the marine industry (Palucka and Bensaude-Vincent, 2002). Their utilization in the wind industry is an even later advancement as per the WTB manufacturers' and original equipment manufacturers' (OEMs) statements of having around 40 years of experience in the wind industry (Nordex-Acciona, Vestas, GE-LM Wind Power, and Siemens Gamesa). When we look at the WTB market today, around 15 % of the global WTB manufacturing capacity (150 GW in 2022) was met by Europe (GWEC, 2023; Rystad Energy, 2023). In 2022, Europe had a wind turbine blade (WTB) manufacturing capacity of 25 GW. Spain, Germany, Denmark, and France led WTB production, accounting for over 60 % of the capacity. TPI Composites, Inc. was estimated to dominate the WTB market, with 12 % of the manufacturing capacity. Many Western wind turbine original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) sourced WTBs from TPI (Rystad Energy, 2023). For instance, TPI supplies products to, e.g., Vestas and Nordex from their WTB manufacturing facilities in the US, Mexico, Turkey, and India in adherence to specifications and design requirements given by the OEMs (TPI, 2023). Accordingly, we have not found information on WTB models produced by TPI; however, we have identified a total of 60 wind turbine models, 6, 22, 25, and 7 models, respectively, from Nordex, Vestas, LM Wind Power, and Siemens-Gamesa on their websites ([Wind turbine blade models], n.d.-a, n.d.-b, n.d.-c, n.d.-d, n.d.-e), all of which are known for their strong presence in WTB manufacturing as OEMs in Europe (Rystad Energy, 2023). We assume each wind turbine model requires a different blade design and construction based on its rated power, size, and other technical characteristics. This implies that at least 60 WTB models are used in Europe today. As most manufacturers rarely disclose the detailed material composition or exact chemical constituents of WTB materials (Juntikka et al., 2018; Mattsson et al., 2020), we tried to find material data of the existing WTB models, motivated by chemical composition understanding of WTBs when they become a secondary source for new material manufacture (Jensen and Skelton, 2018; Bennet et al., 2021). But Vestas, Siemens Gamesa, and LM Wind Power released Product Disposal Specifications for one WTB model each, available on their websites, and recently, a Blade Material Passport (Vestas V47, Siemens Gamesa B45, LM 37.3 P2) that resulted from a collaborative effort of the project DecomBlades, 2021–2023. The fourth document we have found is a draft for an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) about an LCA study, which is again a product of an academy-industry partnership in the project "RecycleWind" (Arndt et al., 2023). The declaration is prepared for rotor blade family EU120.2500 and is owned by TPI Composites Germany GmbH. It includes documentation on the material composition of three blade models tailored to the recycling processes and information on the possible dismantling of individual assemblies and main components relevant to recycling. Even though the release of these four documents in the last two years indicates a positive change, the confidentiality of information is still very dominant in the wind industry, affecting the lifecycle management of WTBs, impeding appropriate repair and maintenance interventions, and sustainable EoL

decisions. To overcome this problem, studies have been identifying mainstream WTB models and analyzing their material composition and impacts using available information from bills of materials, manufacturers' brochures, specifications, or interviews with the manufacturers (Liu et al., 2019; Topham et al., 2019a).

WTB material technology is constantly evolving to produce more durable and lighter blades. The sectoral motivations for developing new materials and processes are multifaceted: (i) prolonging the lifetime of blades, (ii) increasing the size of blades, (iii) improving conversion efficiency, (iv) reducing costs, (v) ensuring a stable supply chain in the face of depleting fossil-based raw materials, (vi) lowering the carbon footprint, and (vii) enhancing recyclability (WindEurope, Cefic and EuCIA, 2020). Innovations in material development focus on modified thermosetting composites, thermoplastic composites, and natural fiber composites (Dorigato, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2021). As technological advancements quicken, standardization or homogenization of WTB waste material is not expected (Juntikka et al., 2018). In this light, material passports and how they should be prepared in the future are crucial for reusing WTB materials at EoL.

3.2. Quantification of expected end-of-life wind turbine blades

We identified 21 studies in our literature search that presented quantitative data regarding WTB decommissioning.

We compiled a database detailing the number of installed and decommissioned wind turbines per European country, distinguishing between onshore and offshore installations and the results are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The major challenges we faced in collecting data were the variation in results and the difficulty of integrating data due to the use of different outcomes in the studies, e.g., range of time, geographical scope, and material type. One major difference lies in data delivery, whether it results from a statistical collection (Sultan et al., 2018; IRENA, 2019; Jensen et al., 2020; WindEurope, 2020a; WindEurope, 2020b; Tota-Maharaj and McMahan, 2021) or the development and application of a quantification method. The quantification methods differ in their results, too, as the methods are constructed for different purposes with different steps and parameters. Their outcomes can be the number of wind turbine blades (Juntikka et al., 2018; Ozturk and Karipoglu, 2022), the amount of FRP composite blade waste material (Liu and Barlow, 2015; Andersen et al., 2016; Liu and Barlow, 2017; Tazi et al., 2019; Lichtenegger et al., 2020; Haces-Fernandez, 2020; Delaney et al., 2021; Cooperman et al., 2021; Martini and Xydis, 2023), or decommissioning of installed wind power capacity as is the case with studies using statistical research. Some distinguish between glass and carbon fiber-reinforced plastic waste in their estimation (Lefevre et al., 2019; Sommer et al., 2020; Volk et al., 2021), and some authors focus on building a spatial database of the aging wind turbines as a base for the planning and preparing of recycling infrastructures (Sultan et al., 2018; Delaney et al., 2021; Cooperman et al., 2021). A few studies adopt a whole lifecycle approach and consider manufacturing and service waste in addition to EoL WTB waste (Liu and Barlow, 2017; Heng et al., 2021). Industry reports provide data on the expected or targeted deployment of windpower installations (IEA, IRENA, WindEurope, GWEC, Rystad). Some of these reports are not included in our analysis because their data are either short-term or do not contain aggregated data per European country. Only a few studies from the industry have an overview of the numbers for the expected volumes of decommissioned blades (WindEurope, 2020b), annual installation, and decommissioning data per country (BTM Consult and GWEC – F. Zhao, personal communication, April 11, 2023), and age distribution of wind capacity (WindEurope, 2020a). Some projects run jointly by industry stakeholders and academic partners also provide data on future decommissioning in installed wind power capacity (Bennet et al., 2021; Bennet et al., 2022).

To overcome the incomparability problem in the results from the literature, we used the BTM Consult and GWEC numbers, the most complete and extensive dataset available, to determine the magnitude of

WTB waste in European countries (F. Zhao, personal communication, April 11, 2023). It contains aggregated annual installation data per country until 2021. Assuming an operational life span of 20 years, we transformed annual installation data simply by shifting the numbers for 20 years. Country data of predicted decommissioning onshore and offshore wind power [MW] in Europe is figured until the year 2043 as Tables S1 and S2 in the Supplement. We then added extra data (GWEC, 2023) for a bigger picture of European decommissioning volume. Decommissioning numbers in Europe are depicted for onshore and offshore installations until 2048 (Fig. 6). However, it should be noted that a 20-year operational lifetime is an average assumption, and the exact lifetime of WTBs is unpredictable, even though the manufacturers define their original design lifetime in the first place. In fact, the actual decommissioning numbers fell far behind the predictions between 2016 and 2022, which highlights the difficulty of making an accurate estimation of this waste stream based on the time of installation and expected lifetime only. This simple translation can be assumed as a worst-case scenario for evaluating EoL-FRP materials occurring in the wind industry.

The Europe-wide increase in cumulative decommissioned onshore wind power capacity (Fig. 6) is expected to be >25-fold in 20 years from now (to 188 GW) and around 40-fold in 25 years (to 284 GW) compared to the calculated decommissioning capacity in 2027 (7 GW). Germany, Spain, and France have the most significant share in European onshore decommissioning numbers (Table S1). For offshore wind power (Fig. 6), the cumulative decommissioned capacity would increase around 50-fold by 2033 and 750-fold by 2048 (from 90 MW in 2027 to 4 GW and 68 GW, respectively). UK, Germany, and the Netherlands are leading in the aging capacity of wind turbines (Table S2). Denmark is also expected to be among the first countries to decommission wind turbines based on age distribution studies of their capacity (WindEurope, 2020a).

The waste amounts of EoL WTB-FRP for each country can be determined using the numbers in Fig. 6 and Tables S1 and S2, with the help of the expected 1 MW = 12–15 tons of composites (Ierides and Reiland, 2019). In the best-case scenario, where 1 MW produces 12 tons of waste, Europe's onshore wind decommissioning capacity generates slightly <3.5 million tons of FRP waste – almost *one-fifth* of the global onshore waste in 2048 - while Europe's offshore wind decommissioning capacity produces slightly >800 thousand tons of waste - almost *one-third* of the global offshore waste. (Fig. 7).

As the figures for wind power installations show a significant rise to reach the 2050 vision, decommissioning numbers could skyrocket by 2050 and beyond. Installation rates entail scaling up offshore wind while onshore wind remains the dominant technology. Europe's onshore wind installed capacity is projected to increase from 164 GW in 2018 to

215 GW by 2030 and 483 GW by 2050 (IRENA, 2019). European Commission proposes to increase Europe's offshore wind capacity from its 2020 level of 12 GW to at least 60 GW by 2030 and to 300 GW by 2050 (EC, 2020). This is equivalent to an increase to over 20 GW offshore per year by the mid-2030s, whereas it is around 3 GW today and 7 GW by the second half of the 2020s (WindEurope, 2019). Therefore, the wind industry needs to shift its focus onto future decommissioning and EoL WTB numbers and support academic research in its efforts to develop and standardize quantification methods to provide precise data that can be used in any region for any WTB type, considering the effects of repowering projects and second-hand markets.

3.3. Waste treatment technologies and decommissioning

Waste management is considered a sub-process of decommissioning, as we advocate the integration of appropriate waste treatment technologies in the EoL of a WTB as the right action towards a more sustainable wind industry. Research on FRP waste treatment technologies or sustainable alternatives to landfill and incineration in EoL scenarios was observed mainly in the 2020s. We compiled 71 studies investigating waste management and treatment technologies and decommissioning of EoL-WTBs. These studies are elaborated under Section 3.5 about the circularity strategies.

3.3.1. Comparison of waste treatment technologies according to some sustainability impact categories

The current methods of waste treatment for thermoset FRP (Table 1) are mechanical, thermal, and chemical processes. We exclude landfills and incineration without energy recovery from the analysis, assuming they do not count as circular options. The ideal recycling case is to obtain recyclates with the same properties as the raw materials at a low cost in the most environmentally friendly way. These methods can reclaim fibers, fillers, and resin from the FRP material, but technical barriers and commercialization challenges can lead to more landfilling and incineration activities.

The reclaimed fibers from EoL WTBs are not as clean as virgin fibers and have resin residues on them (Liu et al., 2019). They possess different lengths due to multiple stages of mechanical pre-processing, which are necessary before thermal and chemical waste treatments (Shuaib and Mativenga, 2016; Liu et al., 2019; Ierides and Reiland, 2019; Xue et al., 2022). Mechanical grinding deteriorates its mechanical properties proportionally with size reduction (Xue et al., 2022). Mechanical properties change drastically because of the high temperature and pressure levels they are exposed to during thermal and chemical treatments (Pickering, 2006). Consequently, the tensile strength of the fibers compared to

Fig. 6. Distribution of cumulatively decommissioned onshore and offshore wind power [MW] in Europe (Source of data: BTM Consult and GWEC – F. Zhao, personal communication, April 11, 2023).

Fig. 7. Cumulative FRP waste originating from EoL WTBs in Europe and in the world, distinguished between onshore and offshore wind farm decommissioning (Source of data: BTM Consult and GWEC – F. Zhao, personal communication, April 11, 2023).

virgin fibers decreases (Pickering, 2006; Liu et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2022), and surface characteristics worsen (Pickering, 2006; Tahir et al., 2021).

Table 2 lists each waste treatment technology's technology readiness levels (TRL). Due to low technological maturity, it is difficult to predict how long it will take for recycling thermoset FRPs to be ready for use. Modern mechanical grinding and cement co-processing are the most mature technologies for glass-FRP (GFRP) WTb, whereas pyrolysis is the ready-to-go carbon-FRP (CFRP) WTb technology. Although commercialized, fibers recovered through mechanical grinding have low-grade mechanical properties. Cement co-processing is ultimately the endpoint for EoL WTb circularity, where the polymer part of FRP is burned as a fuel, and the (glass) fibers become a component of cement mixtures. Solvolysis is the most promising technology for the future, with high yield rates of the recovered material and particularly very good retained tensile strength values for CFRP. Fluidized bed and high voltage pulse fragmentation (HVF) are still at the lab scale. Reclaimed CF shows better mechanical properties than reclaimed GF when pyrolysis, fluidized bed, and solvolysis are used since CF degrades less with high temperatures and pressures (Pickering, 2006). This implies that the increasing trend in CFRP blade design and manufacture will create more volume for these technologies.

When we look at the net profits from using a particular technology (Table 3), mechanical grinding and solvolysis are today's most favorable EoL options for GFRP. The costs and capacities for these technologies also favor mechanical grinding. Comparing the net profits of CFRP waste treatment technologies, we can observe that all options are profitable, discarding the landfill and incineration as waste management solutions. Mechanical grinding is still at the pilot scale, and its profitability is the lowest for CFRP despite having the lowest initial investment fixed and operational costs. Pyrolysis is the only TRL9 recycling technology for CFRP and requires a relatively low budget to build and operate the plant. Lastly, solvolysis generates the biggest profits with significantly higher initial investment and pre-processing costs (Table 3). Therefore, being at the pilot scale, solvolysis is also a promising technology for the future if its financial performance is improved and the technological capacity is increased – according to the current values (Table 3). Costs, TRL, and the treated material capacities are closely related, according to what we observe (Tables 2 and 3). TRL and treated material capacities are relatively proportional; improvement in that would decrease the waste treatment prices.

Pre-processing, such as separation and shredding before any recycling activity, is less energy-intensive than recycling (Shuaib and Mativenga, 2016). Based on the environmental impact compilation in Table 4, mechanical grinding consumes significantly less energy – even

less than virgin production, and has lower global warming potential (GHG) than other thermal and chemical technologies. In the meantime, it is highly comparable to landfill and incineration in both energy demand and GHG. Thus, mechanical grinding makes it the most favorable EoL option for WTb to divert from landfills and incineration. The comparison among other technologies discloses a wide range of energy demand reported – in or close to the range of virgin production, probably because of the non-existing standardization of the recycling processes and the necessary equipment. In addition, a previous study on CFRP mechanical grinding has found that energy demand for GFRP is slightly lower, which can be explained by the better processability of GFRP (Shuaib and Mativenga, 2016). Regarding greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), thermal and chemical technologies could reach similar values with mechanical grinding if technologies are improved further. Only solvolysis has a wide range of GHG, most probably due to differences in the sub-technologies of solvolysis.

3.3.2. Decommissioning

Possible scenarios for EoL, either of a wind farm or WTb, involve lifetime extension, repowering, and decommissioning (Topham et al., 2019a; Bennet et al., 2021; Delaney et al., 2021; Mello et al., 2022; Woo and Whale, 2022). The 20-year operational lifetime is average for WTb, and the unpredictability of the exact service lifetime is due to several reasons: component damage (IEA Wind, 2020a, 2020b; WindEurope, 2020a), ending of the permit period (WindEurope, 2020a; Pakenham et al., 2021; Woo and Whale, 2022), or implementation of a repowering project to the wind farm (WindEurope, 2020a; Pakenham et al., 2021). The first option should be reusing the EoL WTb according to CE principles (Skelton, 2017; Velenturf, 2021; Woo and Whale, 2022; Bennet et al., 2022). In this case, the WTb might need repairs and refurbishment and could be sold in the second-hand market. For example, higher electricity prices and governmental support for small-scale production in Ireland made buying older and less efficient wind turbines from Sweden possible. In contrast, private Swedish clients have bought second-hand wind turbines from the Netherlands for an extra energy supply (Juntikka et al., 2018). Also, WTb manufacturers and O&M service providers are providing upgrades (Liu et al., 2019), which could effectively reduce the manufacturer's need for new WTb. However, Gamesa predicts that the WTb will show more structural problems in root connections and bonding after the WTb pass their designed service life (Liu and Barlow, 2017). When reuse is not an option, the WTb is decommissioned and prepared for waste treatment. As WTb refurbishment belongs to the reuse concept without changing its function, and the WTb will eventually come to the end of its useful service life and must be decommissioned, we focus on decommissioning and partly repowering

Table 1

Comparative description of the fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) waste treatment technologies (Sources: Liu et al., 2019; Ierides and Reiland, 2019; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020; Xue et al., 2022; Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Nagle et al., 2022).

Input	Waste Treatment Technology / Strategy	Output	Technology features	Advantages	Disadvantages/Challenges
Scrap FRP, heat, fuel/coal, clay, limestone	Cement co-processing	Heat, cement clinker	Sending shredded WTB with other waste to a cement kiln for use as fuel and raw material substitution	Highly efficient and fast process, Treatment at large capacities, Up to 75% substitution of cement raw materials and reduction of carbon emissions of the cement industry, No ash left over.	Loss of original material (fiber), Need for additional energy input to reach high processing temperatures, Pollutants and particulate matter emissions
Scrap GFRP/CFRP, electric current, water	High Voltage Pulse Fragmentation (HVPF)	Matrix pieces, fibers	Using high-voltage electrical discharges to disintegrate the polymer matrix in a vessel filled with water or electrolytes	Extraction of longer and cleaner fibers, High retention of fiber tensile strength, Scalability to treat larger capacities, Need for relatively low investment to reach the next TRL.	Recovery of short fibers only, Reduced elasticity of glass fibers, High energy consumption to obtain high-quality fibers, Availability of only lab- and pilot-scale machines, Working near high-voltage
Scrap CFRP, solvents, heat	Solvolysis	Mineral compounds, fibers, resin chemicals	Using sub-/super-critical fluid methods, or chemical depolymerization or removal of the matrix to get clean fibers	Clean fiber recovery at full length, Resin recovery (oligomers or polymers), Lower temperatures compared to thermal technologies, Low-risk solvents, e.g., alcohols, glycols, and supercritical water.	Insufficient process efficiency, High temperature, high-pressure, high-energy consumption, Use of large amounts of solvents, Gas emissions and ecotoxicity, High investment and running costs, Recycling CFRP only
Scrap GFRP/CFRP, hot air/nitrogen.	Fluidized bed	Fibers, fillers, clean fumes	Burning resin matrix as energy and reclaiming fibers	Cleaner fiber surface than pyrolysis without resin residue, Treatment of mixed material (e.g., painted surfaces or foam cores), Simple process, Energy and Precursor chemical recovery, Efficient heat transfer.	More fiber degradation than solvolysis and pyrolysis, Reduced tensile strength of fibers, High process-related emissions, Economically viable if processing capacity > 10,000 t/year
Scrap GFRP/CFRP	Pyrolysis	Fibers, fillers, resin, char, hydrocarbon products, hot gases	Obtaining pyrolysis gas, pyrolysis oil, and solid by-products at high-temperature conditions	Self-sustained process (pyrolysis gas and oil can be used as process energy input), Scalability to multi-ton capacity, An economically sound process for recycling CFRP.	Sensitive optimization of the reaction temperature and time, Oxidation residue / char on the recovered fibers, Degradation of the glass fibers (size and chemical structure), Reduced tensile strength and elasticity of fiber, Not economically viable for glass fibers.
Scrap GFRP/CFRP	Mechanical grinding	Particles, matrix-rich powder, fiber-rich powder	Cutting, crushing, and grinding to obtain different particle sizes from WTB	Efficient technology, Low production cost, Simple process, Commercial scale use	Small, unstructured, coarse, and non-consistent fiber recovery, Recyclate with a high content of other materials (polymers, contaminants, coatings), Up to 40% waste material generation, Fine dust release into the environment.
Sectioned FRP WTB	Functional repurposing	Resized FRP WTB	Cutting, bonding to other materials	FRP material structure preserved, Simple process, Very low production cost	Small scale application

scenarios that could involve waste treatment technologies as a first step in circularity, i.e., manufacturing new materials.

Beatrice Offshore Wind Farm Demonstration Project (10 MW) in the UK, consisting of the largest wind turbines in the world of its time, ceased to operate in 2015. The abandonment commenced in 2017. According to the Decommissioning Project Plan in Beatrice Decommissioning Programmes, 2018 a decommissioning schedule was outlined for until 2032, covering the selection and definition of options and execution (Repsol Sinopec, Resources UK, 2018). Considering the dates of actions, 14 years of decommissioning after a 2-year delay after the announced EoL shows a lack of a clear demolition program and decommissioning strategy as part of the installation and operation plans. The necessity of decommissioning planning is yet to be understood in

the wind industry, as is the decommissioning experience low. This can be confirmed by the low number of decommissioned wind farms in Topham et al. (2019b): 6 offshore wind farms. According to the Elmwind Project report (Bennet et al., 2022), the offshore wind industry prioritizes profit maximization over decommissioning, which is also supported by the company statements in the study by Winkler et al. (2022). On the other hand, insufficient detail in decommissioning planning often results in underestimation of decommissioning costs (Bennet et al., 2021). Reviewed programs show significant differences in decommissioning timings and costs from reality (Topham and McMillan, 2017), £ billions of undercosting due to the changing or uncertain conditions in legislation, availability or high prices of technical equipment, and the perfunctory nature of the decommissioning planning

Table 2

Technical comparison of the fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) waste treatment technologies and recyclates (Sources: Liu et al., 2019; WindEurope, Cefic and EuCIA, 2020; Fonte and Xydis, 2021; Bennet et al., 2021; Chikha et al., 2022; Xue et al., 2022).

Waste Treatment Technology / Strategy	TRL	Retained Tensile Strength, [%]	Fibrous recyclate benefit (yield rate of recycled fiber), [%]	Overall recyclate benefit (final yield rate of recycled fiber, resin, and fillers), [%]	E-modulus, [%]	Recovered fiber, [%]
Functional repurposing	8	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Mechanical grinding	9 (GFRP) 6 (CFRP)	70-78 (GF) 50 (CF)	58	55	90	58-60
Pyrolysis	6 (GFRP) 9 (CFRP)	≤ 50 (GF) 80-95 (CF)	70	67	100	39-83
Fluidized bed	4 (GFRP) 5 (CFRP)	50 (GF) 75 (CF)	44 (GF) 90 (CF)	42 (GF) 86 (CF)	100	66
Solvolytic	5 (GFRP) 6 (CFRP)	60-75 (GF) 90-95 (CF)	100	95	N/A	45-95
High Voltage Pulse Fragmentation (HVF)	4 (GFRP) 4 (CFRP)	88 (GF) 83 (CF)	60	57	-	80.5
Cement co-processing	9 (GFRP)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

*TRL 1–4: Lab Scale, TRL 5–7: Pilot Scale, TRL 8–9: Commercial scale.

Table 3

Economic comparison of the fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) waste treatment technologies and recyclates (Sources: Sommer and Walther, 2021; Liu et al., 2022).

Waste Treatment Technology / Strategy	vGF cost, [\$ /t]	rGF cost, [\$ /t]	Net profits - GF, [\$ /t]	vCF cost, [\$ /t]	rCF cost, [\$ /t]	Net profits - CF, [\$ /t]	Investment cost, [€ /unit]	Operational costs, [€ /t]	Fixed prices, [€ /unit]	Capacity, [ths *t/a]
Mechanical grinding	1300	411	284	23640	3166	3011	250,000	100	15,000	4-15
Pyrolysis	1300	241	-142	23640	6479	6076	900,000	1100	108,000	1
Fluidized bed	1300	176	-230	23640	6303	5877	1,000,000	10000	120,000	1
Solvolytic	1300	1488	606	23640	13992	13090	6,400,000	1500	768,000	1
High Voltage Pulse Fragmentation (HVF)	1300	587	-176	23640	10064	9281	2,450,000	6120	294,000	0.1
Incineration	1300	58.7	-132	23640	58.7	-132				
Landfill	1300	0	-62	23640	0	-57				

Table 4

Environmental comparison of the fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) waste treatment technologies and recyclates (Sources: Shuaib and Mativenga, 2016; Liu et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2022).

Waste Treatment Technology / Strategy	Energy demand, vGF production, [MJ/kg]	Energy demand, rGF production, [MJ/kg]	Energy demand, rCF production, [MJ/kg]	Average energy demand, [MJ/kg]	GHG (CFRP), [kg CO ₂ eq/kg]
Mechanical grinding	13–54	0.17–1.93	0.27–2.03	0.3	0.085–1.8
Pyrolysis	13–54	3–30	12.53–37.36	21.2	0.96–5.4
Fluidized bed	13–54		7.7–9.98	22.2 (GFRP) 9.0 (CFRP)	1.56–2.9
Solvolytic	13–54	61–93	19.2–170.84	19.2	1.53–16.2
High Voltage Pulse Fragmentation (HVF)	13–54	4		16.2	
Cement co-processing				-4.2	
Incineration			0.95–1.71	-4.2	2.17–3.12
Landfill			0.4–1.1	0.3	0.024–0.14

(Jensen et al., 2020).

Decommissioning is not simply the reverse of installation and commissioning as opposed to authors claiming otherwise (Kerkvliet and Polatidis, 2016; Topham and McMillan, 2017; Juntikka et al., 2018; Diani et al., 2022). Instead, it involves (1) preliminary planning of dismantling and disposal, (2) reviewing legislation and achieving permits, (3) tendering and awarding, (4) execution planning, (5)

decommissioning execution, i.e., removal of components; (6) logistics; (7) waste management and treatment, (8) monitoring and maintenance of the site after decommissioning (Topham et al., 2019b; WindEurope, 2020a; Winkler et al., 2022). These steps indicate major differences from initial commissioning, mainly in the EoL management strategies, different technologies, and additional stakeholders. Also, there are many uncertainties in the decommissioning process, including technical,

economic, environmental, and legislative aspects. The review study of available Decommissioning Plans by [Jensen et al. \(2020\)](#) reports slight improvement regarding material recycling specifications, waste management, and a lack of practical and specific guidelines for decommissioning, possibly because plans are too generic and formulaic ([Jensen et al., 2020](#)). According to another review study, waste management procedures could be more developed, with most uncertainties rooted in poorly positioned decommissioning legislation ([Bennet et al., 2021](#)). The outcomes of these two studies represent a chicken-and-egg situation as without legislation; decommissioning plans seem not to show improvement in sustainable EoL management for the WTB materials and without more examples in decommissioning, especially in the lack of technological development for waste treatment and industrial capacity, meaningful legislation cannot be prepared.

Decommissioning activities start with blasting or carefully dismantling the wind turbine using a crane. It is important that dismantling (teardown as in [Cooperman et al., 2021](#)) is carefully carried out so that the different components retain their value for circularity and for processing with waste treatment technologies, particularly EoL WTBs ([Beauson et al., 2022](#)). Dismantling is generally regulated by national legislation, e.g., Energy Sources Acts, Ministerial Decrees, Environmental Codes, or Building Codes in countries such as Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, and the Netherlands ([WindEurope, 2020a](#)). German regulations do not deal with wind turbines only but include auxiliary facilities, access roads, ground sealing, and site restoration ([WindEurope, 2020a](#)). Most EoL WTBs are currently sent to landfills. They first need pre-processing for logistics by cutting them into large segments and then transporting them to the landfill site. However, the lack of legislative standards for cutting techniques and their environmental impacts was highlighted by a logistics company ([Winkler et al., 2022](#)) and in a study by [Lund et al. \(2023\)](#). In some cases, WTBs are shredded before being transported and landfilled, saving space and decreasing final logistics costs ([Cooperman et al., 2021](#); [Liu et al., 2022](#)). This mass-efficient procedure also reduces transport related GHG emissions from a life cycle perspective ([Juntikka et al., 2018](#); [Ierides and Reiland, 2019](#)) and could even lead to an increase in WTB recycling activity and reduce landfilling ([Walzberg et al., 2022](#)). As transportation is identified as a major contributor to decommissioning costs, studies have developed spatiotemporal methods to evaluate road routes linking recycling facilities or wind farms ([Haces-Fernandez, 2020](#); [Ghosh et al., 2022](#)), databases showing the location and timing of WTBs reaching EoL ([Delaney et al., 2021](#)), and mathematical decision support systems for process costs minimization ([Diani et al., 2022](#)). One other aspect regards current practices of sorting and separation of EoL waste material streams – it is carried out manually ([Ierides and Reiland, 2019](#)). Shredded mixtures received for material research or recycling technology development contain not only FRP material but also wood, metal, and others ([Mamanpush et al., 2023](#)).

In ideal future cases where landfilling and incineration are discarded in exchange for sustainable recycling solutions, new challenges await the wind industry. To put waste treatment technologies into a decommissioning and waste management framework after the WTBs are dismantled, we need to understand these challenges regarding how decommissioning projects connect to the EoL WTB waste lifecycle and look for circular solutions for true sustainability in the wind industry. A circular EoL WTB waste lifecycle intersects with a decommissioning project in the 5th, 6th, and 7th steps, namely (5) decommissioning execution, i.e., removal of components, (6) logistics, and (7) waste management and treatment. It follows a journey of dismantling, sorting and separation, on-site pre-processing, storing, transport to recycling facilities, post-processing, and end-destination in secondary applications. To avoid EoL WTB being disregarded in the decommissioning plans, the content of these plans should be standardized, and the EoL options should be well-understood. Also, identifying a clear destination for the dismantled WTB could be helpful in the planning of the decommissioning processes. However, it isn't easy to foresee what

technologies could be ready for recycling thermoset FRPs when the decommissioning is planned in the design or installation stages of the blade's lifecycle.

3.4. Supply chain

Wind supply chain stakeholders include (i) the owner of the wind turbine generator (WTG) or wind farm, (ii) original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and/or composite material manufacturers, (iii) wind farm operators, (iv) decommissioning service providers, and maritime or crane contractors, (v) transport contractors, (vi) waste management company, and (vii) the authority ([WindEurope, 2020a](#); [Bennet et al., 2022](#); [Winkler et al., 2022](#)). The wind farm owner (i) is responsible for downstream supply chain activities, but operators (iii) are responsible for executing these activities. Sometimes, they are the same company ([WindEurope, 2020a](#)). Operators (iii) are accountable for planning, monitoring, and decommissioning, but their core competency is electricity production. Thus, they prefer relying on third-party experts for EoL management ([Bennet et al., 2022](#); [Winkler et al., 2022](#)). Decommissioning service providers (iv) are responsible for on-site waste categorization, planning, and proper execution of demolition in compliance with environmental, health, and safety regulations, whereas waste management companies (vi) receive dismantled materials and execute complete disposal, including all logistical measures (v) ([WindEurope, 2020a](#)). As a result, waste management companies (vi) take the lead role in recycling and disposal ([Rentizelas et al., 2022](#)).

In a linear economy, technical solutions are often undermined by regional and behavioral factors such as regulatory context, current practices, and logistical constraints ([Walzberg et al., 2022](#)). [Martinez-Marquez et al. \(2022\)](#) propose a multi-stakeholder approach, and [Winkler et al. \(2022\)](#) stress the importance of collaborative communication, information sharing, and joint knowledge creation to understand stakeholders' differing perceptions of decommissioning challenges. In France, a communication plan is prepared to ensure dialogue between stakeholders and EoL management ([WindEurope, 2020a](#)). In the UK, DPs are prepared in line with the UK Energy Act 2004, making wind farm operators financially responsible for managing decommissioning as in the "polluter pays" principle ([Jensen et al., 2020](#)). [Mackie \(2023\)](#) questions the legal framework for onshore wind farms in England. The lack of established best practices in decommissioning management creates a knowledge gap, leading to varied legislative approaches. Additionally, regional differences may hinder effective policy design ([Walzberg et al., 2022](#)). At this point, [WindEurope \(2020b\)](#) suggests a European platform to share best practices in recycling composites and consolidating composite waste volumes from all sectors for a more secure waste stream. Within the wind industry, there appears to be a noticeable lack of proactivity in taking the lead of EoL management in the DPs and a tendency to wait-and-see approach for improvements to the best practice and technologies or decommissioning experiences from other wind farms ([Jensen et al., 2020](#)).

Regarding OEMs' role in downstream EoL management, their involvement is only possible with regulation ([Winkler et al., 2022](#)). OEMs in the Scottish offshore wind market prioritize material technology and new orders over managing decommissioned WTBs ([Bennet et al., 2022](#)). Thus, sharing responsibilities with other actors in the downstream collaborative supply chain is suggested ([Jensen and Skelton, 2018](#)), and EPR implementation is being discussed, which implies OEMs taking back EoL WTBs for refurbishment, reuse, and recycling ([Cherrington et al., 2012](#); [WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020](#); [Majewski et al., 2022](#)). OEMs in other regions are exploring cross-industry cooperation to establish recycling facilities or symbiosis processes fed from different industries' WTB and composite waste ([Juntikka et al., 2018](#)). Similarly, some operators, such as Vattenfall and Ørsted, are pushing decommissioning service providers to offer recycling and/or reuse options in their contracts ([Bennet et al., 2022](#)). Waste management companies are attempting to form consortia or joint companies with

supply chain stakeholders to apply for decommissioning tenders at a European level and share risks and financial burdens (Winkler et al., 2022).

Sustainability concerns can be addressed in downstream supply chain by understanding stakeholders' motivations and channeling them into viable business cases. Recycling companies, for instance, shoulder all the responsibility and merely receive 10 % of the costs associated with offshore decommissioning projects (Winkler et al., 2022). Another challenge – the lack of information transparency from OEMs and operators, as discussed in Section 3.1 – can be solved through non-disclosure agreements, which effectively keep confidential information private within the supply chain (Winkler et al., 2022). To tackle the uncertainty surrounding EoL WTb material volume mentioned in Sections 3.2 and 3.3.1, cross-industry cooperation could be employed to secure stable streams to recycling facilities besides developing precise quantification methods. Regarding technological developments, there is a need to match material processability with recycling technology and perform accurate capacity calculations based on material flow and uncertainty analyses. The wind industry's growth will unquestionably affect the supply-demand balance; material flow pathways and collection systems will open more facilities. Calculations show that the average distance from the wind farm to mechanical grinding facilities and other recycling facilities is 386 km (Liu et al., 2022), and the two facilities with the largest capacity for waste material catchment are in Germany and Switzerland. However, scenarios for 2050 indicate higher WTb waste material supply and estimations of an increased number of treatment facilities (Rentizelas et al., 2022). Reducing uncertainties will help address challenges related to proper decommissioning management and end-destination of EoL WTbs.

3.5. Circular economy of wind turbine blades for construction

CE needs to be addressed in the whole product value chain, from resource extraction and WTb manufacturing to collecting and processing discarded products. We categorized studies in literature using the R-ladder concept, particularly R10 by Potting et al. (2017), according to waste prevention strategies, waste treatment technologies, and secondary uses of EoL WTb waste studied in them (Table 5). A higher level of circularity is achieved as the ladder is climbed from R9 to R0. However, the studies discussing circularity levels R0-2 are not in abundance, and can be exemplified in Piasecka et al. (2020); Piotrowska and Piasecka (2021); Rathore and Panwar (2022); Fernandes et al. (2022); Gennitsaris et al. (2023). Each R-strategy places different demands on innovating or enabling technology, product design, and revenue models (Potting et al., 2017). The implications of R-strategies in the wind industry are explained in Table 5, too, by adapting definitions and examples found in Jensen and Skelton, 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; WindEurope, 2020b; Bennet et al., 2021.

Recycling (R8) and repurposing (R7) technologies are relevant to aerospace, marine, automotive, oil&gas, construction, sports, defense, and wind industries (Bennet et al., 2021). However, recycling outputs do not achieve enough quality for downstream reuse, hindering their use in producing new WTbs or other products e.g., construction materials. The literature revealed 47 studies exploring higher Rs such as the lifetime extension of EoL WTbs through material and mechanical innovations, such as André et al. (2020, 2022); Geiger et al. (2020); Joustra et al. (2021); Kalkanis et al. (2019); Karavida and Peponi (2023); Khalid et al. (2023); Novais et al. (2018); Rani et al. (2021); Ratner et al. (2020); Sakellariou (2018) to name a few. Recovery (R9), the least favorable option in terms of circularity, was investigated by Chen et al. (2021); Chiesura et al. (2020); Deeney et al. (2021); Nagle et al. (2020). Recycling (R8) was the most investigated option for EoL WTbs, including Chiesura et al. (2020); Eligüzül and Özceylan (2022); Glosser et al. (2022); Jani et al. (2022); Paulsen and Enevoldsen (2021); Psomopoulos et al. (2019); Smoleń et al. (2022); Yang et al. (2022): 32 studies investigated pyrolysis and microwave pyrolysis, 22 fluidized bed, 17

solvolysis, and 14 studies of HVF technologies to valuable (Table 5). Accordingly, post-processing techniques are needed to improve the quality of recycling outputs and their potential for circularity in other applications. This is possible in several ways, such as fiber sizing, classification, and alignment or fiber surface treatment (Ierides and Reiland, 2019). The particle size of treated FRP waste affects the scope of different applications, e.g., use as filler or reinforcement and use in BMC, SMC, thermoplastics, wood plastic composites, mortar, concrete, or asphalt (Xue et al., 2022). Calibration of FRP waste concentration, particle size, curing time, and superplasticizers can also improve the mechanical properties, workability, porosity, microcracks, and durability when used in concrete (Xue et al., 2022). On the other hand, what is seen as a defect can be beneficial in some applications. Fibers with epoxy resin residue have better chemical and mechanical bonding behavior than virgin fibers when used in 3D-printed polylactic acid filament (PLA) components, resulting in good performance regarding stiffness, tensile strength, and failure strain (Tahir et al., 2021). More experimental studies are needed to test different materials and support the growth of the application range of EoL WTbs in the construction industry (Table 6).

The wind industry is set on improving the quality of material used in WTbs, and therefore more innovative product use and manufacture (R0-R2) strategies must be considered for future potential EoL applications of WTb. We found 19 studies developing these aspects and evolving material usages in WTbs, e.g., modified thermosets, thermoplastics, carbon fiber, and natural fiber use. Such changes in the material composition will change CE practices of EoL WTb down through the R10 ladder, from the effectiveness of repair and maintenance procedures for lifetime extension (R3-R6) to the usability of waste treatment strategies and technologies for repurposing and recycling EoL WTbs in secondary applications (R7-R9). This prompts the importance of material passports discussed in Section 3.1 to allocate proper end use of the recycled/repurposed materials from EoL WTbs.

4. Results and discussion

This review discusses the industry's challenges and how WTb waste could be handled in the coming decades. The EoL management of WTbs represents a significant obstacle in the rise of the wind industry as the industry has yet to come up with a sustainable after-use solution. The relevant literature acknowledges that industrial upscaling of waste treatment technologies is needed to reach higher TRLs and become competitive to recycle the expected volume of WTb in the future (WindEurope, 2020b; Fayyaz et al., 2023). This, in turn, requires the commercial guarantee of the upcoming FRP waste amount (Majewski et al., 2022). Therefore, the development of treatment technologies and the processing costs primarily depend on the quantification and location of WTb waste streams and material flows. Estimating incoming WTb waste volumes is crucial for storing, logistics, and recycling phases (Winkler et al., 2022). 29 GW, 14 GW, and 2.2 GW of projects are expected to become older than 20 years, 25 years, and 30 years old by the end of 2026 in Europe (WindEurope, 2022). That means approximately 45 GW will reach EoL and require a decision of repowering, lifetime extension, or decommissioning in only 3 years. In the meantime, the material flows are affected by other environmental and legislative factors. For example, the existence of a second-hand market for WTb reuse in repowering projects reduces the material flows into the waste treatment facilities in the short term. However, the reused WTbs will eventually reach EoL and be treated with a technology whose pathway could differ in time.

Based on the analysis of available waste treatment technologies and decommissioning activities, we propose improvements in sustainable materials management that best suit the EoL WTbs and cross-sectoral cooperation for circularity with the construction industry to mitigate the climate impacts of both industries. Accordingly, better decommissioning handling requires an integrative approach, including

Table 5
Circularity “R” categorization of the studies.

Circular Strategies R-10	Strategy Description (Potting et al., 2017)	Strategy or Technology Explanation in WTB Terms	References
Smarter product use and manufacture	R0 Refuse	Decreasing natural resources and material consumption in a product chain for delivering the same function with a radically different material	Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Velenturf, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2023; Jensen et al., 2020; Walzberg et al., 2022; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
	R1 Rethink	Decreasing natural resource and material consumption in a product chain for delivering the same function by intensive use or multi-functionality	Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Velenturf, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2023; Jensen et al., 2020; Walzberg et al., 2022; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; ETIP Wind, 2019; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
	R2 Reduce	Increasing product manufacture or use efficiency by applying R0 and R1	Waste reduction, energy minimization, water use reduction, raw material reduction in product development and manufacture

Extend the lifetime of the product and its parts			(reduction efforts in design)	
	R3 Reuse	Reuse by another consumer of discarded product and fulfilling the same function	Use of WTBs again for the same function, e.g., second-hand markets and repowering projects	Majewski et al., 2022; Beauson et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Cooperman et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Sakellariou, 2018; Woo & Whale, 2022; Mello et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Geiger et al., 2020; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Velenturf, 2021; Bennet et al., 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; IRENA, 2019; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
	R4 Repair	Repair and maintenance of defective product to continue using with its original function	Preventative maintenance planned or ad hoc inspection/servicing tasks to maintain a good working condition.	Majewski et al., 2022; Beauson et al., 2022; Woo & Whale, 2022; Pettas & Cheng, 2018; Jensen et al., 2020; Bennet et al., 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
	R5 Refurbish	Restore an old product and bring it up to date.	Repairs and minor replacements of WTB parts as it is new, e.g., for repowering projects	Majewski et al., 2022; Cooperman et al., 2021; Sakellariou, 2018; Woo & Whale, 2022; Piasecka et al., 2020; Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Geiger et al., 2020; Velenturf, 2021; Jensen et al., 2020; Bennet et al., 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; Beauson & Brøndsted, 2016; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
	R6 Remanufacture	Use parts of discarded products in a new product with the same function	Major repairs and replacements of WTB parts for performance upgrade as it is new, e.g., for repowering projects	Sakellariou, 2018; Velenturf, 2021; Gennitsaris et al., 2023; Jensen et al., 2020; Bennet et al., 2021
	R7 Repurpose	Use discarded product or its parts in a new product with a different function.	All mechanical processes that resize or reshape WTBs to use in secondary applications for different functions	Delaney et al., 2021; Chikha et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2020; Mamanpush et al., 2020; Novais et al., 2018; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Geiger et al., 2020; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Velenturf, 2021
			EoL WTB structure repurposing: Using WTBs again for different functions, e.g., acoustic barriers on roadways.	Majewski et al., 2022; Martini & Xydis, 2023; Beauson et al., 2022; Karavida & Peponi, 2023; Sakellariou, 2018; Woo & Whale, 2022
WTB waste sections repurposing: Sectioning WTBs to use in secondary applications for different functions, e.g., furniture and bridge fabrication			Majewski et al., 2022; Martini & Xydis, 2023; Beauson et al., 2022; André et al., 2020; Cooperman et al., 2021; Karavida & Peponi, 2023; Sakellariou, 2018; Woo & Whale, 2022; Ozturk & Karipoglu, 2022; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Geiger et al., 2020; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Joustra et al., 2021; André et al., 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; Beauson & Brøndsted, 2016; Deeney et al., 2021; Juntikka et al., 2018; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020	

Useful application of materials		WTB waste particles repurposing: Mechanical grinding/ <i>Mechanical recycling</i> of WTBs to use in secondary applications for different functions, e.g., as reinforcement or aggregate in concrete	Majewski et al., 2022; Martini & Xydis, 2023; Paulsen & Enevoldsen, 2021; Rentizelas et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2021; Beauson et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Fonte & Xydis, 2021; Cooperman et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Sakellariou, 2018; Tahir et al., 2021; Ghosh et al., 2022; Woo & Whale, 2022; Chiesura et al., 2020; Ratner et al., 2020; Psomopoulos et al., 2019; Ozturk & Karipoglu, 2022; Heng et al., 2021; Oliveira et al., 2020; Mamanpush et al., 2020; Figiela et al., 2022; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Jani et al., 2022; Khalid et al., 2023; Rahimzadeh et al., 2021; Mamanpush et al., 2018; Baturkin et al., 2021; Plawecka et al., 2021; Yazdanbakhsh et al., 2018; Cherrington et al., 2012; Dorigato, 2021; Baturkin et al., 2022; Mamanpush et al., 2023; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Sommer & Walther, 2021; Gennitsaris et al., 2023; Bennet et al., 2021; Beauson & Brøndsted, 2016; Walzberg et al., 2022; Kalkanis et al., 2019; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020	
	R8 Recycle	All recycling technologies for processing materials to obtain high-grade or low-grade constituents	Separating composite structure of WTBs to reclaim constituent materials, i.e., fibers, resins, oils	Martini & Xydis, 2023; Eligüzel & Özceylan, 2022; Mello et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021; Ozturk & Karipoglu, 2022; Piasecka et al., 2020; Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Geiger et al., 2020; Glosser et al., 2022; Baturkin et al., 2021; Velenturf, 2021; Topham et al., 2019a; Diani et al., 2022; Jensen et al., 2020; Bennet et al., 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; WindEurope, 2020b
		Thermal recycling technologies	All high-temperature treatments to WTBs reclaim fibers while recovering energy from the polymer part of the composites.	Beauson et al., 2022; Sakellariou, 2018; Khalid et al., 2023; Beauson & Brøndsted, 2016
		*Pyrolysis, microwave pyrolysis		Majewski et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022; Paulsen & Enevoldsen, 2021; Chikha et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2021; Smoleń et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Fonte & Xydis, 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Tahir et al., 2021; Woo & Whale, 2022; Chiesura et al., 2020; Ratner et al., 2020; Psomopoulos et al., 2019; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Jani et al., 2022; Cherrington et al., 2012; Dorigato, 2021; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Sommer & Walther, 2021; Lewandowski et al., 2019; Gennitsaris et al., 2023; Mishnaevsky, 2023; Bennet et al., 2021; Walzberg et al., 2022; Kalkanis et al., 2019; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
		*Fluidized bed		Chikha et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022; Fonte & Xydis, 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Woo & Whale, 2022; Chiesura et al., 2020; Ratner et al., 2020; Psomopoulos et al., 2019; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Jani et al., 2022; Cherrington et al., 2012; Dorigato, 2021; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Sommer & Walther, 2021; Bennet et al., 2021; Kalkanis et al., 2019; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
*Thermolysis		Rani et al., 2021		

		Chemical recycling	All chemical treatments to WTBs to reclaim fibers and polymers	Beauson et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2019; Sakellariou, 2018; Woo & Whale, 2022; Jani et al., 2022; Khalid et al., 2023; Cherrington et al., 2012; Dorigato, 2021; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Bennet et al., 2021; Beauson & Brøndsted, 2016; Kalkanis et al., 2019
			•Solvolysis, solvolysis/HTL "Hydrothermal liquefaction"	Majewski et al., 2022; Mattsson et al., 2020; Paulsen & Enevoldsen, 2021; Chikha et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2021; Beauson et al., 2022; Cooperman et al., 2021; Jensen & Skelton, 2018; Sommer & Walthner, 2021; Mishnaevsky, 2023; Bennet et al., 2021; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
			•HVF "High voltage pulse fragmentation" (Electro-chemical recycling)	Majewski et al., 2022; Chikha et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Cooperman et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Woo & Whale, 2022; Sommer & Walthner, 2021; Bennet et al., 2021; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020
			•Hydrolysis	Rani et al., 2021; Cooperman et al., 2021; Skelton, 2017
			•Glycolysis	Rani et al., 2021
		Hybrid technologies	Combination of recycling technologies	Rani et al., 2021; Khalid et al., 2023
	R9 Recover	Incineration, Cement co-processing	The organic content of the waste is recovered as thermal energy (recovery). In contrast, the mineral fraction of the waste can be integrated (hence recycled) into the matrix of the product or material produced, e.g., cement clinker.	Majewski et al., 2022; Paulsen & Enevoldsen, 2021; Beauson et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Fonte & Xydis, 2021; Cooperman et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Karavida & Peponi, 2023; Ghosh et al., 2022; Woo & Whale, 2022; Mello et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021; Chiesura et al., 2020; Psomopoulos et al., 2019; Ozturk & Karipoglu, 2022; Heng et al., 2021; Martinez-Marquez et al., 2022; Nagle et al., 2020; Rathore & Panwar, 2022; Sommer & Walthner, 2021; Valenturf, 2021; Jensen et al., 2020; Bennet et al., 2021; Deeney et al., 2021; Walzberg et al., 2022; Ierides & Reiland, 2019; Juntikka et al., 2018; ETIP Wind, 2019; Skelton, 2017; WindEurope, 2020b; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020

technological, economic, environmental, and legislative aspects.

4.1. Conceptual framework for circular end-of-life strategies for wind turbine blades

CE has a multipurpose role in EoL WTBs and needs to be well-adjusted to the existing market and supply chain structure. Fig. 8 forms the backbone of our review, allocating the different stakeholders of the wind industry along the R10 framework as well as the specific practices found in the literature review. Decommissioning is identified as the key stage of this framework (Fig. 8), as it is always present at the end of the WTB lifecycle, even after the life extension and repowering solutions were implemented. Decommissioning entails a series of processes at the beginning of the WTB-waste lifecycle that will affect the design of secondary applications in other industries. Hence, it is necessary to account for the stakeholders' roles in the WTB supply chain and the capability and capacity of the FRP waste treatment technologies in the overall framework.

Major gaps found with this framework that would hamper the circularity and sustainability of EoL management of WTBs are:

- Lacking material composition data of WTBs
- Uncertainty in the future decommissioning numbers and volume of WTB waste
- Uncertainty in the capacity of technologies to treat WTB FRP waste
- Unprecedented and complex challenges in decommissioning of WTBs
- Reactivity of decommissioning-stage stakeholders and knowledge gap in their responsibilities

It is evident from the techno-economic comparison of waste treatment technologies – mainly recycling (R8) – that a legislative

background is needed to improve the technologies to deal with the EoL WTB sustainably. EU-level policies relevant to WTB treatment can be found in several works (Juntikka et al., 2018; WindEurope, 2020a; WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020; Bennet et al., 2021; Beauson et al., 2022) and they show limited regulations for FRP waste and EoL WTB treatment, with misaligned national and international legislation. Also, standards should be considered for the application of EoL WTBs in the development of other products outside the wind supply chain. Therefore, a Europe-wide harmonized legislative setup that includes improvements to the definitions and the design of the existing legislative instruments and fills in the need for incentives for sustainable waste treatment technologies is needed. Finally, this setup should offer practical solutions for a circular economy that works in practice.

4.2. Regulatory implications for sustainable wind turbine blade waste management

A regulatory framework could set boundaries and roadmaps for the industry, especially regarding EoL WTBs. Although the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) prioritizes recycling and reusing, which includes limiting incineration to non-recyclable material and phasing out landfilling to non-recyclable and non-recoverable waste (Juntikka et al., 2018), more specific guidelines may be required for a successful implementation of the CE framework to the wind industry. We list some suggestions below.

A first step into a harmonized legislative setup for EoL WTB in Europe would be correctly characterizing and defining the waste type. WTB waste is identified with different codes based on other legislation, although the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) is used as the most common categorization where WTB is regarded as plastic waste from construction and demolition with the code 17 02 03 (WindEurope,

Table 6
Examples from the literature for recycling and repurposing of end-of-life wind turbine blade (WTB) waste for material innovation in the construction industry.

Input from end-of-life WTB	Secondary application	Test area	Reference
Pulverized WTB waste as a partial replacement for sand	Cementitious mortar	Mechanical properties	Oliveira et al., 2020
Mechanically ground WTB waste	Thermoplastic composites	Mechanical and physical properties	Mamanpush et al., 2018; Mamanpush et al., 2020; Mamanpush et al., 2023
Mechanically milled and classified WTB waste	Composite panels	Thermal, mechanical, physical, and fire resistance properties	Figiela et al., 2022
Mechanically ground WTB waste	Geopolymer materials/ aluminosilicate cement	Mechanical properties	Figiela et al., 2022
GFs from pyrolyzed WTB waste	Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) based composites	Processability and mechanical properties	Lewandowski et al., 2019
Mechanically ground and classified WTB waste	Polylactic acid filament (PLA) production	Mechanical and thermal properties	Rahimizadeh et al., 2021
Mechanically processed WTB waste as a partial replacement of cement or aggregate and as fiber reinforcement	Concrete	Mechanical properties, chemical composition	Baturkin et al., 2021; Baturkin et al., 2022
Mechanically ground WTB waste as a filler	Geopolymer composites	Physical and mechanical properties, chemical composition	Plawecka et al., 2021
Slender elements cut from WTB waste as a partial replacement of coarse aggregate	Concrete	Mechanical properties	Yazdanbakhsh et al., 2018

Cefic and EuCIA, 2020). According to the European List of Waste established as part of the Commission Decision 2000/532/EC, WTBs are labeled non-hazardous waste. However, the labeling system is intricate and can confuse users on the waste of multiple materials and lead to inconsistencies (Beauson et al., 2022).

Second, landfill and incineration options could be phased out if they have effective bans and taxation. Landfill prices are already commonly used as a legislative instrument. Rentizelas et al. (2022) collected the typical charges of gate fees and landfill tax for 2020 per country in Europe. Accordingly, Romania, Slovakia, Portugal, Malta, and Croatia have the lowest typical charges for landfilling, all below or equal to €20. The maximum amounts are in Italy, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Sweden, and the UK – above €140. The rest of the European countries have a landfilling price range between €40 and €130. Although pricing can be used as a dissuading strategy, some countries are already banning the landfill of FRP products, such as Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, and Finland (WindEurope, 2020a). However, landfill bans and taxes must be well-designed to avoid unintended consequences. For example, the 3rd edition of the National Waste Management Plan of the Netherlands exempts wind farms from the landfill ban if alternative solutions exceed the benchmark value of €200/t (WindEurope, 2020a).

A third option would be to establish a Europe-wide regulatory framework that incentivizes the use of sustainable waste treatment technologies, as recommended by Majewski et al. (2022). Germany and

Fig. 8. A conceptual framework for CE integration into the WTB lifecycle with decommissioning in focus. Credit: Ashal Tyurkay. (Image sources: IEA Wind, 2020a; Echidna Technologies Pty Ltd, n.d.; Freepik, n.d.-a, n.d.-b; LIFE-BRIO, 2014-2017; Katsikopoulou, 2021; Jacoby, 2022).

France are taking immediate actions: (i) France limits rotor mass recycling targets to a minimum of 35 %, 45 %, and 55 % effective from 2022, 2023, and 2025, respectively (WindEurope, 2020a); (ii) France and Germany are discussing Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) which implies that the Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) take back the EoL WTBs, but it proved ineffective. In France, it was suggested that joint efforts between authorities and the industry would be more likely to be successful. In Germany, an EU-level solution was advocated for the integrity of the EU internal market rather than applying EPR in Germany in isolation (WindEurope, Cefic, and EuCIA, 2020).

A fourth policy action would be to regain the recycled materials in other materials' manufacturing, i.e., recycling in an open-loop. Reclaiming fibers, fillers, or resin is not enough for the industry's sustainability unless its economic value is utilized in designing and manufacturing environmentally sustainable products. For this reason, recycling outputs should have a characterization and potential use definition – supporting Bennet et al. (2021) main conclusions.

The authors urge the wind industry to prioritize decommissioning procedures and allow for strategic actions such as inter-sectoral industrial symbiosis rather than waiting for recycling technologies development. As illustrated in Fig. 9, the sectoral challenges can be addressed more easily if awareness and proactivity are provided in the industry. This can be supported by recognizing academic expertise and industrial R&D in the field of EoL WTB treatment and CE. Finally, policy can contribute to this improvement with a reasonable regulatory framework.

Fig. 9. Ways to address sectoral gaps and challenges in EoL WTB management.

4.3. Limitations

Our literature review covers the references published between 2014 and 2023, with a very high number from the last four years and an exception (Pickering, 2006) which deals with thermoset composite recycling technologies regardless of the industry. This is partly because the field is still emerging and the understanding of the WTB EoL issues both in research and practice is limited. It was imperative to add industry reports and private communications in the industry next to the sources found on academic databases to cover all the latest developments and latest data, as well as to understand the wind industry's position. This helped us to better identify and evaluate strengths and weaknesses within the industry. Given the limited flow of knowledge and low decommissioning experience in the supply chain, we addressed the problematic issues in the wind industry that might hamper the circularity transition.

Varying estimates from different waste calculation methods had a limiting impact on the study but reported waste amounts sufficiently indicate the WTB waste problem significance. However, the uncertainties in lifetime expectancy and waste numbers hinder finding the geographical and strategic starting point for a circularity route. The uncompetitive low-mature waste treatment technologies restrict the description of circularity remedies in detail. A coupling effort between industries and expanding the study scope to construction material development would require investigating the needs for the second-generation FRP-based material range and sustainability requirements for such development in the construction industry.

Despite the supremacy of this subject in importance, and due to the extensivity of environmental and economic assessments, we focused on the possibility of introducing EoL WTB materials into the construction industry. The framework presented in this study can serve as a basis for future research on circularity transition in the wind industry. The addition of the revealed economic advantages of different recovery/recycling technologies and the precise waste volumes could turn this framework into an effective circularity tool in the future.

5. Conclusion

The data we collected estimates that the projected 3-fold onshore and 20-fold offshore capacity growth in 20 years in Europe would mean the cumulative production of 3 million tons of EoL WTB FRP waste, of which the responsibility is not currently allocated to the industry and, therefore, the supply chain is not prepared for this amount of waste. CE would allow an economic and social transformation with changes in the whole supply chain instead of focusing only on waste and environmental

pollution.

Based on the review findings and discussions, we list below our recommendations to maximize the sustainable circularity in the EoL management of WTBs that also shed some light on a future roadmap.

Wind industry should make efforts to create a more transparent supply chain and to develop a standard procedure for dismantling and decommissioning WTBs in Europe with:

- Material passports for WTBs
- Tracing material constituents of WTBs
- Non-disclosure agreements to share data between the supply chain actors
- Development of business cases that integrate waste treatment technologies into decommissioning
- Development of a standard procedure for dismantling and decommissioning WTBs in Europe
- Early design stage planning of the decommissioning and optimization of routes
- Development of on-site WTB pre-processing techniques and the sorting/separation of waste material streams to embed CE strategies at the EoL easier

Academia could support the wind industry with:

- Development of precise quantification methods and standardization thereof to estimate the future decommissioning capacity and WTB waste at the region/country level, distinguished between onshore and offshore
- Technical development of waste treatment technologies
- Quantification studies for WTB waste per waste treatment technology
- Technical, economic, environmental and social studies for sustainable dismantling and decommissioning of WTBs
- Qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the construction market in its material range for the use of second-generation FRP-based material coming from decommissioned WTBs

In addition to regulatory improvements discussed in Section 4.2, policy should motivate the wind industry and/or enforce:

- A more transparent and trusting environment for manufacture and material documentation
- Collaboration in the supply chain

- Creation of economic motivation regarding decommissioning and waste treatment activities for all parties besides the environmental benefits of possible decarbonization strategies in the wind industry

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ashal Tyurkay: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Gunvor M. Kirkelund:** Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Ana Teresa Macas Lima:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 101096437. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

The authors would like to thank the Blades2Build partners for their collaboration that made this research possible as well as the reviewers for their valuable contribution.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.03.018>.

References

- [Wind turbine blade models] (n.d.-a). Web: <https://www.ge.com/renewableenergy/wind-energy/leading-wind-turbine-blade-technology> Accessed: 16th June 2023.
- [Wind turbine blade models] (n.d.-b). Web: <https://www.lmwindpower.com/en/services/technology-centers> Accessed: 16th June 2023.
- [Wind turbine blade models] (n.d.-c). Web: <https://www.nordex-online.com/en/company/> Accessed: 16th June 2023.
- [Wind turbine blade models] (n.d.-d). Web: <https://www.siemensgamesa.com/en-int/products-and-services> Accessed: 16th June 2023.
- [Wind turbine blade models] (n.d.-e). Web: <https://www.vestas.com/en/products> Accessed: 16th June 2023.
- Andersen, N., Eriksson, O., Hillman, K., Wallhagen, M., 2016. Wind turbines' end-of-life: quantification and characterization of future waste materials on a national level. *Energies* 9 (12), 999. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9120999>.
- André, A., Kullberg, J., Nygren, D., Mattsson, C., Nedev, G., Haghani, R., 2020. Re-use of wind turbine blade for construction and infrastructure applications. *Iop Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 942 (1), 012015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012015>.
- André, A., Magdalena, J., Cecilia, M., Georgi, N., Haghani, R., 2022. The re-use of end-of-life fiber reinforced polymer composites in construction. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 198, 1183–1195. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88166-5_103.
- Arndt, C., Brinkmann, T., Spring, P., Spuziak-Salzenberg, D., 2023. Environmental product declaration 2.0 - rotor blade 2.0 for the rotor blade EU120.2500. EPD-draft referring to ISO 14025 and EN 15804 +A1; status January 2023. Web: https://www.iekrrw.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/20230221_EPD-RecycleWind-2.0_TPL.pdf.
- Baturkin, D., Hisseine, O.A., Masmoudi, R., Tagnit-Hamou, A., Massicotte, L., 2021. Valorization of recycled FRP materials from wind turbine blades in concrete. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 174, 105807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105807>.
- Baturkin, D., Masmoudi, R., Tagnit-Hamou, A., Metiche, S., Massicotte, L., 2022. Feasibility study on the recycling of FRP materials from wind turbine blades in concrete. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 198, 1729–1742. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88166-5_150.
- Beauson, J., 2022. End-of-life of wind turbine blades – value chain, recycling and composite materials. *DTU Wind and Energy Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.11581/dtu.00000221>.
- Beauson, J., Brøndsted, P., 2016. In: Ostachowicz, W., McGugan, M., Schröder-Hinrichs, J.U., Luczak, M. (Eds.), *Wind Turbine Blades: An End of Life Perspective*. MARE-WINT. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39095-6_23.
- Beauson, J., Madsen, B., Toncelli, C., Brøndsted, P., Bech, J.I., 2016. Recycling of shredded composites from wind turbine blades in new thermoset polymer composites. In: *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 90. Elsevier, pp. 390–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.07.009>.
- Beauson, J., Laurent, A., Rudolph, D.P., Pagh Jensen, J., 2022. The complex end-of-life of wind turbine blades: a review of the European context. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 155, 111847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111847>.
- Bennet, L., Velenturf, A., Fitzgerald, A., Lightfoot, J., Fuller, J., Hailey, J., Lomoro, P., 2021. Sustainable Decommissioning: Wind Turbine Blade Recycling. Technical Report. From: https://ore.catapult.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/CORE_FuII_Blade_Report_web.pdf.
- Bennet, L., Spyroudi, A., Stevenson, L., 2022. End of Life Materials Mapping for Offshore Wind in Scotland: Report from Phase 1 of the Elmwind Project. Technical Report, From: <https://ore.catapult.org.uk/?orecatapultreports=end-of-life-materials-mapping-for-offshore-wind-in-scotland>.
- Chen, Y., Cai, G., Zheng, L., Zhang, Y., Qi, X., Ke, S., Liu, G., 2021. Modeling waste generation and end-of-life management of wind power development in Guangdong, China until 2050. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 169, 105533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105533>.
- Cherrington, R., Goodship, V., Meredith, J., Wood, B.M., Coles, S.R., Vuillaume, A., Kirwan, K., 2012. Producer responsibility: defining the incentive for recycling composite wind turbine blades in Europe. *Energy Policy* 47, 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.03.076>.
- Chiesura, G., Stecher, H., Pagh Jensen, J., 2020. Blade materials selection influence on sustainability: a case study through LCA. *Iop Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 942 (1), 012011. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012011>.
- Chikha, I., Bouzidi, Y., Tazi, N., Baklouti, S., Idir, R., 2022. Comparative study between different valorization methods of glass fiber waste from end-of-life wind turbine blades. 13th international renewable Energy congress. *Irec* 2022, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IREC56325.2022.10002104>.
- Cooperman, A., Eberle, A., Lantz, E., 2021. Wind turbine blade material in the United States: quantities, costs, and end-of-life options. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 168, 105439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105439>.
- Cortés, E., Sánchez, F., O'Carroll, A., Madramany, B., Hardiman, M., Young, T.M., 2017. On the Material Characterisation of Wind Turbine Blade Coatings: The Effect of Interphase Coating–Laminate Adhesion on Rain Erosion Performance. *Materials* 10 (10), 1146. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma10101146>.
- Deeney, P., Nagle, A.J., Gough, F., Lemmert, H., Delaney, E.L., McKinley, J.M., Graham, C., Leahy, P.G., Dunphy, N.P., Mullally, G., 2021. End-of-life alternatives for wind turbine blades: sustainability indices based on the UN sustainable development goals. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 171, 105642. *ISSN* 0921-3449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105642>.
- Delaney, E.L., McKinley, J.M., Megarry, W., Graham, C., Leahy, P.G., Bank, L.C., Gentry, R., 2021. An integrated geospatial approach for repurposing wind turbine blades. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 170, 105601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105601>.
- Diani, M., Picone, N., Gentilini, L., Jensen, J.P., Angius, A., Colledani, M., 2022. Disassembly of large composite-rich installations. *Systemic Circular Economy Solutions for Fiber Reinforced Composites* 37–60. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22352-5_3.
- Dorigato, A., 2021. Recycling of thermosetting composites for wind blade application. *Advanced Industrial and Engineering Polymer Research* 4 (2), 116–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiepr.2021.02.002>.
- DTU Library, (n.d.). <https://findit.dtu.dk/>.
- EC, 2020. Boosting offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral Europe. Web: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_2096.
- Echidna Technologies Pty Ltd. (n.d.). Case Study: Wind-turbine Demolition. [Picture] Web: https://echidna.com.au/KnowledgeCorner/case-studies.php?Study=wind_turbine_demolition Accessed: 16th February 2023.
- Eligüzel, İ.M., Özceylan, E., 2022. A bibliometric, social network and clustering analysis for a comprehensive review on end-of-life wind turbines. *J. Clean. Prod.* 380, 135004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135004>.
- European Commission, 2014. Towards a circular economy: a zero waste programme for Europe. In: *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex:52014DC0398>. (Accessed 17 July 2023).
- Fayyaz, S., Lund, K.W., Khoshnevisan, B., Madsen, E.S., Birkved, M., 2023. Sustainable end-of-life value chain scenarios for wind turbine blades. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Online) 2507, 012007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2507/1/012007>.
- Fernandes, A.P., Prado, K.S., Castanho, M.N., Paiva, J.M.F., 2022. Preparation and characterization of polymeric composites assembled from fiberglass fabric waste from the wind blades manufacturing process. *Fibers and Polymers* 23 (13), 3606–3614. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12221-022-4425-4>.
- Figliola, B., Korniejenko, K., Łach, M., Azzopardi, B., 2022. A study on geopolymer composites based on waste from wind turbine blades. *Mater. Werkst.* 53 (4), 467–478. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mawe.202100354>.
- Fonte, R., Xydias, G., 2021. Wind turbine blade recycling: an evaluation of the European market potential for recycled composite materials. *J. Environ. Manage.* 287, 112269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112269>.

- Freepik, (n.d.). Wind turbine concept illustration. [Picture] Web: https://www.freepik.com/free-vector/wind-turbine-concept-illustration_8174456.htm#query=wind%20turbine&position=2&from_view=keyword>Image by storyset Accessed: 16th February 2023.
- Freepik, (n.d.). Energy power flat icons set. [Picture] Web: https://www.freepik.com/free-vector/energy-power-flat-icons-set_4376486.htm#query=wind%20turbine&position=5&from_view=keyword>Image by macrovector_official Accessed: 16th February 2023.
- Geiger, R., Hannan, Y., Travia, W., Naboni, R., Schlette, C., 2020. Composite wind turbine blade recycling - value creation through industry 4.0 to enable circularity in repurposing of composites. *Iop Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 942 (1), 012016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012016>.
- Gennitsaris, S., Sagani, A., Sofianopoulou, S., Dedoussis, V., 2023. Integrated LCA and DEA approach for circular economy-driven performance evaluation of wind turbine end-of-life treatment options. *Appl. Energy* 339, 120951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.120951>.
- Ghosh, T., Hanes, R., Key, A., Walzberg, J., Eberle, A., 2022. The circular economy life cycle assessment and visualization framework: a multistate case study of wind blade circularity in United States. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 185, 106531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106531>.
- Glosser, D., Santyikul, E., Fagan, E., Suraneni, P., 2022. A thermodynamic perspective on wind turbine glass fiber waste as a supplementary cementitious material. *Cement*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cement.2022.100039>.
- GWEC, 2022. Global Wind report 2022. Web: <https://gwec.net/global-wind-report-2022/>.
- GWEC, 2023. Global Wind report 2023. Web: <https://gwec.net/globalwindreport2023/>.
- Haces-Fernandez, F., 2020. Gowind: Wind energy spatiotemporal assessment and characterization of end-of-life activities. *Energies* 13 (22), 6015. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13226015>.
- Heng, H., Meng, F., McKechnie, J., 2021. Wind turbine blade wastes and the environmental impacts in Canada. *Waste Manag.* 133, 59–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.07.032>.
- IEA Wind, 2020a. IEA Wind TCP annual report. Web: <https://iea-wind.org/category/annual-reports/>.
- IEA Wind, 2020b. Task 42 Lifetime Extension Assessment, Deliverable Report D-1: Gap Analysis of Existing Procedures required for Life Extension. Web: <https://iea-wind.org/iea-publications/>. Accessed: 20th Mar 2023.
- Ierides, M., Reiland, J., 2019. Wind turbine blade circularity - technologies and practices around the value chain. Bax&Company. Web: <https://baxcompany.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/wind-turbine-circularity.pdf>.
- IRENA, 2019. Future of wind: deployment, investment, technology, grid integration and socio-economic aspects (a global Energy transformation paper). International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi. Web: https://www.irena.org/-/media/files/irena/agency/publication/2019/oct/irena_future_of_wind_2019.pdf (Accessed: 20th Mar 2023).
- Jacoby, M., 2022. How can companies recycle wind turbine blades? [Picture] Web: <https://cen.acs.org/environment/recycling/companies-recycle-wind-turbine-blade-s/100/i27>. Accessed: 17th January 2023.
- Jani, H.K., Singh Kachhawa, S., Nagababu, G., Das, A., 2022. A brief review on recycling and reuse of wind turbine blade materials. *Materials Today: Proceedings* 62 (13), 7124–7130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.02.049>.
- Jensen, J.P., Skelton, K., 2018. Wind turbine blade recycling: experiences, challenges and possibilities in a circular economy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 97, 165–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.08.041>.
- Jensen, P.D., Purnell, P., Velenturf, A.P.M., 2020. Highlighting the need to embed circular economy in low carbon infrastructure decommissioning: the case of offshore wind. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 24, 266–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2020.07.012>.
- Joustra, J., Flipsen, B., Balkenende, R., 2021. Structural reuse of high end composite products: a design case study on wind turbine blades. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 167, 105393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105393>.
- Juntikka, M., Tränkle, T., Mattsson, C., Sott, R., 2018. Circular economy and the management of end-of-life wind turbine blades. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. Web: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1525435/FULLTEXT05.pdf>.
- Kalkanis, K., Psomopoulos, C.S., Kaminaris, S., Ioannidis, G., Pachos, P., 2019. Wind turbine blade composite materials - end of life treatment methods. *Energy Procedia* 157, 1136–1143. ISSN 1876-6102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.11.281>.
- Karavida, S., Peponi, A., 2023. Wind turbine blade waste circularity coupled with urban regeneration: a conceptual framework. *Energies* 16 (3), 1464. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031464>.
- Katsikopoulou, M., 2021. Wind turbine blades as bike sheds? [Picture] Web: <https://www.designboom.com/design/denmark-repurposing-wind-turbine-blades-bike-garages-09-27-2021/>. Accessed: 10th January 2023.
- Kerkvliet, H., Polatidis, H., 2016. Offshore wind farms' decommissioning: a semi-quantitative multi-criteria decision aid framework. *Sustain Energy Technol Assess* 18, 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2016.09.008>.
- Khalid, M.Y., Arif, Z.U., Hossain, M., Umer, R., 2023. Recycling of wind turbine blades through modern recycling technologies: a road to zero waste. *Renewable Energy Focus* 44, 373–389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ref.2023.02.001>.
- Lefevre, A., Garnier, S., Jacquemin, L., Pillain, B., Sonnemann, G., 2019. Anticipating in-use stocks of carbon fibre reinforced polymers and related waste generated by the wind power sector until 2050. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 141, 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.008>.
- Lewandowski, K., Skórczewska, K., Piszczek, K., Urbaniak, W., 2019. Recycled glass fibres from wind turbines as a filler for poly(vinyl chloride). *Adv. Polym. Technol.* 2019, 8960503. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8960503>.
- Lichtenegger, G., Rentzelas, A.A., Trivyza, N., Siegl, S., 2020. Offshore and onshore wind turbine blade waste material forecast at a regional level in Europe until 2050. *Waste Manag.* 106, 120–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.03.018>.
- LIFE-BRIO, 2014-2017 [Picture] Web: <http://www.lifebrio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/foto3.jpg>. Accessed: 16th February 2023.
- Liu, P., Barlow, C.Y., 2015. An update for wind turbine blade waste inventory. *EWEA 2015 Conference*.
- Liu, P., Barlow, C.Y., 2016. The environmental impact of wind turbine blades. *Iop Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 139 (1), 012032. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/139/1/012032>.
- Liu, P., Barlow, C.Y., 2017. Wind turbine blade waste in 2050. *Waste Manag.* 62, 229–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.02.007>.
- Liu, P., Meng, F., Barlow, C.Y., 2019. Wind turbine blade end-of-life options: an eco-audit comparison. *J. Clean. Prod.* 212, 1268–1281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.043>.
- Liu, P., Meng, F., Barlow, C.Y., 2022. Wind turbine blade end-of-life options: an economic comparison. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 180, 106202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106202>.
- Lund, K.L., Nielsen, M.L., Madsen, E.S., 2023. Sustainability assessment of new technologies using multi criteria decision making: a framework and application in sectioning end-of-life wind turbine blades. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 184, 113542. ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113542>.
- Mackie, C., 2023. Planning, discretion and the legacy of onshore wind. *Leg. Stud.* <https://doi.org/10.1017/lst.2022.50>.
- Majewski, P., Florin, N., Jit, J., Stewart, R.A., 2022. End-of-life policy considerations for wind turbine blades. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 164, 112538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112538>.
- Mamanpush, S.H., Li, H., Englund, K., Tabatabaei, A.T., 2018. Recycled wind turbine blades as a feedstock for second generation composites. *Waste Manag.* 76, 708–714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.02.050>.
- Mamanpush, S.H., Li, H., Englund, K., Tavousi Tabatabaei, A., 2020. Extruded Fiber-reinforced composites manufactured from recycled Wind turbine blade material. *Waste Biomass Valoriz.* 11 (7), 3853–3862. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-019-00659-0>.
- Mamanpush, S.H., Li, H., Tabatabaei, B.T., Englund, K., 2023. The impact of Wood fibers in composite panels made from recycled fiberglass wind turbine blades. *Waste Biomass Valoriz.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-023-02038-2>.
- Martinez-Marquez, D., Florin, N., Hall, W., Majewski, P., Wang, H., Stewart, R.A., 2022. State-of-the-art review of product stewardship strategies for large composite wind turbine blades. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling Advances* 15, 200109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2022.200109>.
- Martini, R., Xydys, G., 2023. Repurposing and recycling wind turbine blades in the United States. *Environmental Progress and Sustainable Energy* 42 (1), e13932. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.13932>.
- Mattsson, C., André, A., Juntikka, M., Tränkle, T., & Sott, R., 2020. Chemical recycling of end-of-life wind turbine blades by solvolysis/HTL. *Iop Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 942 (1), 012013. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012013>.
- Mello, G., Ferreira Dias, M., Robaina, M., 2022. Evaluation of the environmental impacts related to the wind farms end-of-life. *Energy Rep.* 8, 35–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyrep.2022.01.024>.
- Mishnaevsky, L., 2021. Sustainable end-of-life Management of Wind Turbine Blades: overview of current and coming solutions. *Materials* 14 (5), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14051124>.
- Mishnaevsky, L., 2023. Recycling of wind turbine blades: recent developments. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* 39, 100746. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2022.100746>.
- Nagle, A.J., Delaney, E.L., Bank, L.C., Leahy, P.G., 2020. A comparative life cycle assessment between landfilling and co-processing of waste from decommissioned Irish wind turbine blades. *J. Clean. Prod.* 277, 123321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123321>.
- Nagle, A.J., Mullally, G., Leahy, P.G., Dunphy, N.P., 2022. Life cycle assessment of the use of decommissioned wind blades in second life applications. *J. Environ. Manage.* 302 (Part A) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113994>.
- Novais, R.M., Carvalho, J., Capela, M.N., Seabra, M.P., Pullar, R.C., Labrincha, J.A., 2018. Incorporation of glass fibre fabrics waste into geopolymer matrices: an eco-friendly solution for off-cuts coming from wind turbine blade production. *Construct. Build Mater.* 187, 876–883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.08.004>.
- Okoli, C., Schabram, K., 2010. A Guide to Conducting a Systematic Literature Review of Information Systems Research. In: *Sprouts: Working Papers on Information Systems*, 10(26). <http://sprouts.aisnet.org/10-26>.
- Oliveira, P.S., Antunes, M.L.P., da Cruz, N.C., Rangel, E.C., de Azevedo, A.R.G., Durrant, S.F., 2020. Use of waste collected from wind turbine blade production as an eco-friendly ingredient in mortars for civil construction. *J. Clean. Prod.* 274, 122948. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122948>.
- Ozturk, S., Karipoglu, F., 2022. Investigation of the best possible methods for wind turbine blade waste management by using GIS and FAHP: Turkey case. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 30 (6), 15020–15033. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-23256-6>.
- Pakenham, B., Ermakova, A., Mehmanparast, A., 2021. A review of life extension strategies for offshore wind farms using techno-economic assessments. *Energies* 14 (7), 1936. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14071936>.
- Palucka, T., Bensaude-Vincent, B., 2002. History of Composites - Overview. In: *California Institute of Technology*, 19 Oct. 2002. https://authors.library.caltech.edu/5456/1/hrst.mit.edu/hrs/materials/public/composites/Composites_Overview.htm. (Accessed 3 January 2023).

- Paulsen, E.B., Enevoldsen, P., 2021. A multidisciplinary review of recycling methods for end-of-life wind turbine blades. *Energies* 14 (14), 4247. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144247>.
- Piasecka, I., Baldowska-Witos, P., Flizikowski, J., Piotrowska, K., Tomporowski, A., 2020. Control the system and environment of post-production Wind turbine blade waste using life cycle models. Part 1. Environmental transformation models. *Polymers* 12 (8), 1828. <https://doi.org/10.3390/POLYM12081828>.
- Pickering, S.J., 2006. Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials-current status. *Compos. A: Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 37 (8), 1206–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.05.030>.
- Pierce, R., Falzon, B.G., 2017. Simulating resin infusion through textile reinforcement materials for the manufacture of complex composite structures. *Engineering* 3, 596–607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENG.2017.04.006>.
- Piotrowska, K., Piasecka, I., 2021. Specification of environmental consequences of the life cycle of selected post-production waste of wind power plants blades. *Materials* 14 (17), 4975. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14174975>.
- Plawecka, K., Przybyła, J., Korniejewski, K., Lin, W.T., Cheng, A., Lach, M., 2021. Recycling of mechanically ground wind turbine blades as filler in geopolymer composite. *Materials* 14 (21), 6539. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14216539>.
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M.P., Worrrell, E., Hanemaaijer, A., 2017. *Circular Economy: Measuring Innovation in the Product Chain. Policy Report. PBL Netherlands Assessment Agency: The Hague, The Netherlands.*
- Psomopoulos, C.S., Kalkanis, K., Kaminaris, S., Ioannidis, G.C., Pachos, P., 2019. A review of the potential for the recovery of wind turbine blade waste materials. *Recycling* 4 (1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling4010007>.
- Rahimizadeh, A., Kalman, J., Fayazbakhsh, K., Lessard, L., 2021. Mechanical and thermal study of 3D printing composite filaments from wind turbine waste. *Polym. Compos.* 42 (5), 2305–2316. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.25978>.
- Rani, M., Choudhary, P., Krishnan, V., Zafar, S., 2021. A review on recycling and reuse methods for carbon fiber/glass fiber composites waste from wind turbine blades. *Compos. Part B Eng.* 215, 108768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.108768>.
- Rathore, N., Panwar, N.L., 2022. Environmental impact and waste recycling technologies for modern wind turbines: an overview. *Waste Management and Research* 734242X221135527. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X221135527>.
- Ratner, S., Gomonov, K., Revinova, S., Lazanyuk, I., 2020. Eco-design of energy production systems: the problem of renewable energy capacity recycling. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* 10 (12), 4339. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10124339>.
- Rentizelas, A., Triviza, N., Oswald, S., Siegl, S., 2022. Reverse supply network design for circular economy pathways of wind turbine blades in Europe. *Int. J. Prod. Res.* 60 (6), 1795–1814. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1870016>.
- Repsol Sinopec, Resources UK, 2018. Beatrice decommissioning programmes. Web: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/772806/Beatrice_Decommissioning_Programmes.pdf.
- Rystad Energy, 2023. The state of the European wind energy supply chain. In: *Industry Report. Web: WindEurope Market Intelligence Member Area.* Accessed: 16th Jun 2023.
- Sakellariou, N., 2018. Current and potential decommissioning scenarios for end-of-life composite wind blades. *Energy Systems* 9 (4), 981–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12667-017-0245-9>.
- Shuaib, N.A., Mativenga, P.T., 2016. Energy demand in mechanical recycling of glass fibre reinforced thermoset plastic composites. *J. Clean. Prod.* 120, 198–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.01.070>.
- Skelton, K., 2017. *Discussion Paper on Managing Composite Blade Waste. WindEurope.*
- Smoleń, J., Olesik, P., Jala, J., Adamcio, A., Kurtyka, K., Godzierz, M., Boczkowska, A., 2022. The use of carbon fibers recovered by pyrolysis from end-of-life Wind turbine blades in epoxy-based composite panels. *Polymers* 14 (14), 2925. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14142925>.
- Sommer, V., Walther, G., 2021. Recycling and recovery infrastructures for glass and carbon fiber reinforced plastic waste from wind energy industry: a European case study. *Waste Manag.* 121, 265–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.12.021>.
- Sommer, V., Stockschläder, J., Walther, G., 2020. Estimation of glass and carbon fiber reinforced plastic waste from end-of-life rotor blades of wind power plants within the European Union. *Waste Manag.* 115, 83–94. ISSN 0956-053X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.06.043>.
- Sultan, A.A.M., Mativenga, P.T., Lou, E., 2018. Managing supply chain complexity: foresight for wind turbine composite waste. *Procedia CIRP* 69, 938–943. ISSN 2212-8271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2017.11.027>.
- Tahir, M., Rahimizadeh, A., Kalman, J., Fayazbakhsh, K., Lessard, L., 2021. Experimental and analytical investigation of 3D printed specimens reinforced by different forms of recyclates from wind turbine waste. *Polym. Compos.* 42 (9), 4533–4548. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.26166>.
- Tazi, N., Kim, J., Bouzidi, Y., Chatelet, E., Liu, G., 2019. Waste and material flow analysis in the end-of-life wind energy system. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 145, 199–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.02.039>.
- Topham, E., McMillan, D., 2017. Sustainable decommissioning of an offshore wind farm. *Renew. Energy* 102, 470–480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.10.066>.
- Topham, E., McMillan, D., Bradley, S., Hart, E., 2019a. Recycling offshore wind farms at decommissioning stage. *Energy Policy* 129, 698–709. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.01.072>.
- Topham, E., Gonzalez, E., McMillan, D., João, E., 2019b. Challenges of decommissioning offshore wind farms: overview of the European experience. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 1222 (1), 012035. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1222/1/012035>.
- Tota-Maharaj, K., McMahon, A., 2021. Resource and waste quantification scenarios for wind turbine decommissioning in the United Kingdom. *Waste Disposal and Sustainable Energy* 3 (2), 117–144. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42768-020-00057-6>.
- TPI (2023). Investor presentation, June 2023. Web: <https://ir.tpicomposites.com/webistes/tpicomposites/English/0/investor-relations.htm> 1 Accessed: 28th Jul 2023.
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2015. *Adoption of the Paris Agreement FCCC/CP/2015/L.9/Rev.1.*
- Velenturf, A.P.M., 2021. A framework and baseline for the integration of a sustainable circular economy in offshore wind. *Energies* 14 (17), 5540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175540>.
- Volk, R., Stallkamp, C., Herbst, M., Schultmann, F., 2021. Regional rotor blade waste quantification in Germany until 2040. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 172, 105667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105667>.
- Walzberg, J., Cooperman, A., Watts, L., Eberle, A.L., Carpenter, A., Heath, G.A., 2022. Regional representation of wind stakeholders' end-of-life behaviors and their impact on wind blade circularity. *iScience* 25 (8), 104734. ISSN 2589-0042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104734>.
- Welsch, S., 2022. How Much Does a Plane Weigh? Available at: <https://euflightcompensation.com/how-much-does-a-plane-weigh/#:~:text=Typically%2C%20the%20average%20commercial%20aircraft,other%20materials%20transported%20on%20planes.> (Accessed 12 June 2023).
- Wind, E.T.I.P., 2019. How Wind is going circular—blade recycling. Web: <https://etipwind.eu/files/reports/ETIPWind-How-wind-is-going-circular-blade-recycling.pdf>.
- WindEurope, 2017. Repowering and lifetime extension: Making the most of Europe's wind energy resource. WindEurope, Brussels. Web: <https://windeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/files/policy/position-papers/WindEurope-Repowering-and-Lifetime-Extension.pdf>.
- WindEurope, 2019. Our energy, our future. How offshore wind will help Europe go carbon-neutral. Technical Report. Web: <https://windeurope.org/intelligence-platform/product/our-energy-our-future/>. Accessed: 20th Mar 2023.
- WindEurope, 2020a. Decommissioning of onshore wind turbines – industry guidance document. Web: <https://windeurope.org/intelligence-platform/product/decommissioning-of-onshore-wind-turbines/>.
- WindEurope, 2020b. How to build a circular economy for wind turbine blades through policy and partnerships. Position paper. Web: <https://windeurope.org/policy/position-papers/how-to-build-a-circular-economy-for-wind-turbine-blades-through-policy-and-partnerships/>. Accessed: 20th Mar 2023.
- WindEurope, 2022. Wind energy in Europe - 2021 Statistics and the outlook for 2022–2026. Available from: <https://windeurope.org/intelligence-platform/product/wind-energy-in-europe-2021-statistics-and-the-outlook-for-2022-2026/>.
- WindEurope, Cefic and EuCIA, 2020. Accelerating Wind turbine blade circularity. Web: <https://windeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/files/about-wind/reports/WindEurope-Accelerating-wind-turbine-blade-circularity.pdf>.
- Winkler, L., Kilic, O., Veldman, J., 2022. Collaboration in the offshore wind farm decommissioning supply chain. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 167, 112797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112797>.
- Woo, S.M., Whale, J., 2022. A mini-review of end-of-life management of wind turbines: current practices and closing the circular economy gap. *Waste Manage. Res.* 40 (12), 1730–1744. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X221105434>.
- WorldGBC, 2019. World Green Building Council: Bringing embodied carbon upfront – coordinate action for the building and construction sector to tackle embodied carbon. Web: <https://www.worldgbc.org/newsmedia/bringing-embodied-carbon-upfront>. Accessed: 23rd Mar 2023.
- Xue, X., Liu, S.-Y., Zhang, Z.-Y., Wang, Q.-Z., Xiao, C.-Z., 2022. A technology review of recycling methods for fiber-reinforced thermosets. *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.* 41 (11–12), 459–480. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07316844211055208>.
- Yang, W., Kim, K.H., Lee, J., 2022. Upcycling of decommissioned wind turbine blades through pyrolysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* 376, 134292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134292>.
- Yazdanbakhsh, A., Bank, L.C., 2014. A critical review of research on reuse of mechanically recycled FRP production and end-of-life waste for construction. *Polymers* 6 (6), 1810–1826. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym6061810>.
- Yazdanbakhsh, A., Bank, L.C., Rieder, K.A., Tian, Y., Chen, C., 2018. Concrete with discrete slender elements from mechanically recycled wind turbine blades. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 128, 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.08.005>.